

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES
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D5.3 Updated Pilot Scenarios Execution and pilots Evaluation – final version

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ABSTRACT

In this deliverable, framed in the WP5, is a final report of the activities carried out during the nine months of execution of the pilots. This document includes the activities carried out in the pilots, the details of the day of the TSIG Workshop, the evaluation of both the platform and the pilots by the different stakeholders of the project, the attainment of the KPIs and the evaluations end of the work carried out in the WP5.

VERSION HISTORY TABLE

Version no.	Date	Author	Changes
0.1	01/05/2018	FABLAB LECCE	Deliverable ToC
0.15	10/05/2018	AIJU	Changes in ToC
0.2	20/05/2018	JUEMA	Juema Pilot Description
0.25	30/05/2018	V-CUBES	V-Cubes Pilot Description
0.3	10/06/2018	FABLAB LECCE	Pilots Updates
0.4	15/06/2018	FABLAB ROM	Pilots Updates
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0.65	23/06/2018	AIJU	Exploitation and sustainability
0.7	25/06/2018	SINGULAR LOGIC	Platform Walkthrough
0.8	26/06/2018	FABLAB LECCE	Results and conclusions
0.81	26/06/2018	FABLAB ROM	Results and conclusions
0.82	26/06/2018	JUEMA	Results and conclusions
0.83	26/06/2018	V-CUBES	Results and conclusions
0.84	27/06/2018	AIJU	Evaluation and KPIs
0.9	29/06/2018	FABLAB LECCE	Final Integration
1.0	30/06/2018	NTUA	Review

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1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is part of WP5. WP5 is responsible for the overall planning, management and evaluation of the pilot applications. Such pilot scenarios have demonstrated both the scientific innovations and the business value proposition of the overall ToyLabs approach. Moreover, this workpackage has built and engaged the necessary community members that have supported the pilot application, and that from now, will support also the continuity of the Platform utility.

During WP5, project partners have worked together, achieving the following goals:

- Preparing and coordinating successfully the pilot applications proposed in the DoA.
- Creating a guideline for the piloting.
- Executing the pilot scenarios, creating a tool for collecting relevant information about pilots' execution and applying it with satisfactory conclusions.
- Optimizing the ToyLabs Platform, solving bugs, and improving features.
- Enrolling experts in safety, in childhood and also final users in the Platform and pilot activities.
- Assessing impact and added value of the ToyLabs Methodology and Platform successfully.
- Identifying lessons learnt by the piloting phase to be used in the future.

All these achievements are described in this deliverable, which aims to clarify and capture all information regarding the piloting scenarios. This deliverable provides updated documentation of the pilots operation and execution and also documents all lessons learnt from the project. Here is provided a methodological adoption guideline for the utilisation of the ToyLabs platform for future uses of it.

The main objectives of this deliverable are the following:

- Final description of the piloting activities of WP5.
- Main results of piloting activities.
- Key KPIs of the ToyLabs platform in the processes of creation of new products.
- Report of the activities carried out in the TSIG Workshop with childhood experts held in Bucharest.
- Obtaining a guide for the use of the ToyLabs platform, based on the experiences acquired during the piloting period.

That is why the deliverable has been organized in two main parts. In the first of these, "Final Report of Piloting and Execution Activities", is a complete review

of all the activities carried out in the pilots, focusing first and foremost on the scenarios proposed in the DoA, and then developing a description of other activities carried out in the Platform (proposals for new toy creation projects). The second part consists of the description of the activities carried out in the TSiG Workshop organized in Bucharest, attended by a total of nine Childhood Experts from all over Europe with the aim of sharing experiences in the use of the ToyLabs Platform, reflecting on the ability to achieve the proposed KPIs, suggest improvements that they consider necessary, and contribute their knowledge to help define the way the platform is exploited. In addition, this deliverable includes two other specific sections. The first, with the aim of demonstrating the close relationship between the ToyLabs Methodology, the platform and the execution of the pilots. The second, centered on the guidelines for the utilization of the ToyLabs Platform, which will help future users, by gathering information on the operation, characteristics and use of the platform.

Finally, in the conclusions section, the lessons learned during the course of the pilots are detailed, the impact generated by the pilots in each of the consortium organizations is defined and, finally, a reflection is made on the general results of WP5.

2. TOYLABS METHODOLOGY AND PLATFORM INTEGRATION

The ToyLabs Open Innovation & Co-Creation methodology are tightly related to one another despite the fact that the project’s consortium started working on the methodology from the very early stages of the project whereas the platform is the end result. However there is a strong correlation from the methodology to the platform and vice versa. On the one hand, the process that users of the platform are called to follow was a direct result of the methodology and a practical translation of the methodology’s phases in a way that it could make sense in a collaborative ICT platform. On the other hand, the methodology was developed taking into consideration the platform’s three key functionalities (Social Analytics, Partner Matching, and Augmented Reality), given that these were also mentioned in the project’s DOA as part of the objectives and success criteria and as critical parts of the overall approach and solution. As such, they were taken into account during the development of the methodology, which can be seen below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: ToyLabs Methodology

The first connection of the methodology with the platform has to do with the cooperative nature of the model. In other words, the Partner Matching module of

the platform could already be seen in that stage of the project, given that in every phase of the process, the product owner is encouraged to collaborate with a number of stakeholders. As such, the methodology took into account that the final solution would include a tool that allows product owners to seek, find and cooperate with other stakeholders of the toy industry. Following that, in the first phase of the methodology, Immersion, the concept of Trends/Feedback analysis was included as an integral part of it. Even from the proposal, it was considered that an approach based on data analytics can actually create a competitive advantage for toy manufacturing SMEs that oftentimes cannot afford expensive market reports and this is reflected in the methodology. Finally, one of the key suggestions of the methodology has to do with several rounds of feedback gathering and product assessment even from the early stages of the process. This was included because it was considered a fact that Augmented Reality will be used in the final solution to help the product owner receive feedback, especially in the design and prototyping phases. This is also reflected in the methodology's model. It can be concluded that from the beginning of the project, the consortium had a general idea of what the platform would consist of and this fact allowed the creation of a more holistic methodology that takes into account the solutions that were going to be implemented while adding others along the way.

For the development of the platform, the methodology's new toy development process was translated to the platform level as technical specifications and a clear step-by-step procedure. The process, as can be seen in the platform does not include every phase that can be seen in the figure above but it does include all the functionalities that are included in the methodology's model. The platform's phases for new toy development are Concept, Research, Design, Prototype and Production as can be seen in Figure 2. In the next part of the present chapter the correlation between these phases and the methodology will be explained.

Image 1 - ToyLabs Platform Process

Figure 2: ToyLabs platform process for new toy development

The first phase of the platform, Concept asks the product owner to fill in some basic information about his new project such as the name, description, toy category, age groups etc. as well as add some initial images and specification files. Concept definition as it can be seen in the methodology, begins from deciding and writing down the main characteristics of the product under consideration and finishes with the conceptual design of the toy. As such, these two phases are somewhat related because the idea for a new product is at this

point still at a rough stage and subject to change when the product owner has a clearer idea of the market and what he wants to create. The product owner can change this information at any point of the project if the concept changes.

The second phase, Research is a direct result of the Immersion phase, as this was described in the deliverables of WP2. Immersion refers to understanding potential market needs and getting inspired, in order to create a new product or an improved version of an existing one. In the ToyLabs platform it is at this phase that the product owner can take advantage of the Market Trend & Social Feedback module to receive valuable information and insights that can significantly support the evolution of the initial idea to something more specific.

The third phase of the platform, Design is related to the methodology's Prototype Design phase. It is the phase in which the product's design must be developed and finalised. For that reason, the product owner is called to use the Partner Matching module to find FabLabs, Safety/Environmental and childhood experts that will help him by providing ideas and feedback. Moreover, the Augmented Reality module can be used to help the product owner receive even more feedback not only from FabLabs and experts but also from end-users in the cases that the project's design is public. The finalised design from this phase is used as input for the next phase which is Prototyping.

The Prototype phase in the platform is very much the same with the phase of Prototyping as this was presented in the methodology. At this phase, the finalised design is sent to one or more FabLabs to develop tangible prototypes. These prototypes are then assessed by the experts who suggest improvements and provide their feedback. Moreover, much like in the Design phase the Augmented Reality module can be used on the prototype to receive feedback from the experts and end-users. Moreover, at this phase the product owner can explore the possibility of creating localised versions of his toy. When the prototype is finalised, it is sent to production which is handled internally by the product owner (in case he is also a manufacturer which is the most common case).

When the product reaches the Production phase, ToyLabs' contribution in the development of the toy is concluded and the product owner is ready to continue with mass production.

Some more points of interrelation between the methodology and the platform will be explained below. First of all, the right side of the methodology that includes the phases of assessment that are usually performed after the initial production of the toy were integrated to the main process of new toy development and not omitted. This was done to save the product owner both time and money by incorporating feedback provision in each phase to pinpoint potential problems regarding the concept, design and prototype from the early phases and deal with them immediately. Moreover, in the methodology each phase included a number

of small iterative cycles. This is also apparent in the platform where the user is allowed to edit information and specifications about his product at any point and create several versions of a design or prototype.

It can be concluded that the relation between the methodology and the project's platform is very strong. On the one hand, in the main phases of new product development (Research, Design, and Prototype) the methodological steps were turned into technical requirements that were later used to develop the platform and its modules. On the other hand, the assessment phases, as already mentioned were integrated in the procedure instead of being stand-alone phases in the platform. Customer assessment is performed via the augmented reality module whereas the technical assessment (from FabLabs) and the safety & environmental assessment are performed in between the iterations of each phase to make the whole process faster and more precise. What differences can be seen between the methodology and the platform, exist because the platform's new toy development process had to be practical and easy-to-use for the product owner.

3. FINAL REPORT OF PILOTING AND EXECUTION ACTIVITIES

3.1. MAIN PILOT SCENARIOS

As seen in the D5.2, some main pilots have been developed through the use of the platform. In particular, they are:

- 1) Mechanical Puzzle Toys Pilot
- 2) Dolls and Accessories Pilot

Both projects have been uploaded on the platform by the toymakers, and shared with the FabLabs as tests for the project.

3.1.1. DOLLS AND ACCESSORIES PILOT

The Dolls and Accessories Pilot will mostly demonstrate the innovations introduced by ToyLabs as far as it concerns to rapid prototyping, taking advantage of FabLabs manufacturing capabilities, as well as getting feedback and recommendations based on produced prototypes by childhood experts and child-life specialists.

JUEMA is interested in analysing competition and predicting market trends, given such children toys have relatively short lifecycles, so their early identification is important.

3.1.1.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOTING PHASES

This section details the process of executing this pilot in detail. Each of the activities carried out is analyzed, phase by phase, from the conceptualization process to production, through design and prototyping.

JUEMA has the need to create a small copy of the already existing 32 cm doll. Make it shrink from 32 cm to 22 cm approximately, make the shrinkage and the 3D model first in order to change the proportions and a printed model to use for moulds. First, the idea was uploaded by the toymaker on the platform as a “New Product” with the name of “21-22cm Amiga Doll”. Here the product is described, with details about the age to which it is addressed, the category and the state of development.

Image 2 - New Product creation

The first phase, called Concept, which is based on the conceptualization of the idea, provided a brief description of the product to be developed, the target audience, etc. The information has been filled-in and uploaded by JUEMA.

Image 3 - 21-22cm Amiga Doll Concept

After that, a market analysis research with the name “My Little Amiga” has been processed, following the ToyLabs Methodology, and using the Social Analytics and Market Trends Analysis Tool. In this analysis the following keywords were studied: “small doll”, “company”, “pretty”, “favourite toy” and the source types “Facebook” and “Twitter” were activated. The number of mentions of these keywords during a whole year was analysed, in order to discern if there is any type of trend related to these categories.

The screenshot shows the 'My Little Amiga' search configuration page. At the top, there are navigation links for 'Dashboard', 'Members', and 'About', along with a user profile for 'OLGA TRAVINA'. The search area includes a text input field with 'My Little Amiga' and a 'Keywords' section with tags for 'small doll', 'company', 'pretty', and 'favorite toy'. A help box explains search syntax: 'For example by pressing toy, cube, puzzle toy, sphere the tool will search in social media for posts that include the words "toy" and "cube", the exact phrase "puzzle toy" and exclude results that include the word "sphere". In other words this search will return results relevant to puzzle toys that are shaped like cubes but not like spheres. In another example the user could be searching for toys that are shaped like cubes or spheres but are not puzzle toys. In this case the search would look like so: toy, cube, sphere, !puzzle toy'. Below this, the 'Source type' section has 'Twitter' and 'Facebook' selected. The 'Influencers' section has 'Only influencers' selected. At the bottom right, there are 'Save as copy' and 'Update' buttons. The footer contains copyright information for 2017-2018 ToyLabs Consortium and a European Union logo with text: 'The ToyLabs project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 732559.'

Image 4 and 5 – Amiga doll Market Analysis Screenshot

In this analysis it can be seen that with the keyword "doll", we have discovered that there are many mentions since the beginning of April. Moreover, "favorite doll" is also a frequent keyword. We can see at this analysis that there is an increasing interest in dolls during this year and that shows us that the acceptance of the product in the market will be good.

Successively, the design phase was activated.

In the next step, using the form in the platform, the toymaker has sought the collaboration of some FabLab experts in 3D printing and 3D modelling. Moreover, final users gave some feedback.

Image 6 - Partner Matching & Selection Mechanism Screenshot and Final Users Comments

Once they found the two prototypes, they started the collaboration with FabLab Lecce and FabLab Romania. For this purpose, they made use of the “Partner Matching & Selection Mechanism”. With the advanced search tool, they could make a list of FabLabs with 3D Modelling and 3D Printing capabilities, which were the technologies they needed to develop the doll.

In the personal pages of the FabLab, therefore, the project is displayed in the collaboration area within the dashboard.

Image 7 - Collaborations Lists Screenshot

At this point, the collaboration between the Toymaker (JUEMA) and FabLab Lecce begins through the exchange of private messages and comments:

Image 8 - Messages Section Screenshot

In these messages, the following topics were discussed:

- The prototypes that JUEMA needs printed through 3D printing.
- Problems with certain materials, that lead to the need of printing using new more rigid materials.
- Solutions related to problems in the lines of adjustment, proportions, increase in proportions, etc.

Thus the prototyping phase began:

Image 9 – Amiga Doll Design Screenshot

In this phase, once the prototypes were made, the errors were identified and the different versions of the prototype were created:

Image 10 - Second version of the Amiga doll design Screenshot

In the specific case of the doll, the main problem encountered was the wrong choice of print material.

Image 11 - Collaboration section with Amiga Doll Design Screenshot

After an iterative procedure of 4 prototyping phases, the final model has been created. The next picture shows the definitive prototype.

Image 12 - Third Version of Amiga doll design Screenshot

Image 53 - Product Prototypes Section Screenshot

The toymaker can then proceed to the final stage, the doll production.

Image 64 - 21-22cm Amiga Doll creation Process

3.1.1.2. RESULTS OF THE PILOTS

As dolls producer, JUEMA has the need to create moulds for each product it wants to produce. Until the project, the realization of a doll was made by an artisan, who manually created the prototype. Even though the handcraftsmanship was accurate, the tolerance of the parts produced (as legs, neck or arms joint) could not suit perfectly, because it was not realized using a mechanical technology (as 3d printing or cnc machines). Another problem was also found when the doll should be scaled, keeping the same proportion. Thanks to the help of the platform, JUEMA was able to easily identify FabLabs that have made an important contribution.

The use of 3d scanning technology was also very important because it gave the possibility to transform the artisan work into a digital model. In fact, once JUEMA sent the small head and the big body to the FabLab, thanks the 3D scanner, it was possible to create the 3D model of the parts. Thanks to the market trend analysis, present in the platform, JUEMA has been able to modify its initial model, adapting it to the requests of the market where the doll is expected to be sold. In the prototyping phase, after checking the file, JUEMA has provided some feedback referring to the dimension and the shape of the produced model. Based on it, the FabLabs have modified the models and printed them again. JUEMA

was glad to discover some solutions and materials used for prototyping that were very useful to get the final prototype, through the collaboration phases inside the platform. Thanks to the comments and private messages, a series of changes were made. These modifications made it possible to obtain the final prototype using the most suitable material.

3.1.2. MECHANICAL PUZZLE TOYS PILOT

The V-CUBES pilot is ideal for demonstrating the innovative characteristics of ToyLabs, mostly regarding the collection of multi-locales user feedback and the application of augmented reality technologies for providing the worldwide community of V-CUBES enthusiasts with opportunities of virtually experiencing products under consideration and providing their preferences and feedback. Furthermore, given the fact that V-CUBES toys are mostly addressed to children over the age of 10, there are plenty of discussions in social media regarding the niche market of mechanical puzzle cubes and similar toys. As such, in the framework of the pilot, the analytics and market prediction tool will be also utilised in order to get on one hand crowd feedback regarding the existing products of the company and on the other hand to capture the worldwide trends of this market, which are important for V-CUBES in order to take them into account in designing new toys.

3.1.2.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOTING PHASES

With this project, V-CUBES intends to create a new product. This product is characterized by its small size and its manageability. It is intended to create a miniature cube puzzle, which can be hooked on the keys, and, therefore, people can play with it at any time. The first step is to upload the idea on the platform. The toymaker has created this “New Product” with the name “3x3 'V' Pillow Cube for keychain”.

Image 75 - 3x3 'V' Pillow Cube for keychain Concept

The first phase, called “Concept”, has been filled-in and uploaded from VERDES INNOVATIONS S.A.

Successively, a market analysis research with the name “Cubic puzzle Trend Analysis” has been performed, using the Social Analytics & Market Trends Analysis Tool. They chose the following keywords: “cube”, “puzzle”, “rotational”, “keychain”, “brainteaser”, “v-cube”, “rubik’s cube”, “mechanical puzzles” and activated the source type “Facebook” and “Twitter”.

Image 86 and 17 - 'V' Pillow Cube Market and Trend Analysis Screenshots

At the analysis it can be seen that the keywords “cube” and “puzzle” have been a trend since the beginning of February in Facebook and Twitter. Moreover, with the keychain concept, the toy keychain has been the most mentioned one. With these results the manufacturer could begin with the design phase.

After that, the design phase was activated. At this phase, it is possible to add different products, one for each version. For the 3x3 'V' Pillow Cube for keychain, two versions were necessary. Once the second was completed the first one was removed.

Image 18 - 'V' Pillow Cube Designs Screenshot

In this page, the toymaker can choose to start a collaboration with someone else, who can help him accomplish the project. In this case, the FabLabs, as experts in 3D printing and 3D modelling were chosen. With this objective, the manufacturer used the Partner Matching & Selection Mechanism, creating collaborations with FabLab Lecce and FabLab Romania.

Image 19 - 'V' Pillow Cube Collaborations Section Screenshot

In the personal page of the FabLabs, the project is displayed in the collaboration area within the dashboard.

Image 20 - 'V' Pillow Cube Second Design Screenshot

At this point, the collaboration between the Toymaker and the FabLab begins through the exchange of private messages and comments. Most of them concern the design of the different pieces. This feedback helped the FabLab in the task of modelling the pieces accurately for the 3D printing.

Image 21 - Feedback of 'V' Pillow Cube Screenshot

After that, the prototyping phase can start.

A first model was created and shared under the name “V-CUBE PROTOTYPE V1.0”.

Image 22 - 'V' Pillow Cube Prototype Section Screenshot

Some comments about the friction were added, suggesting that, when playing with the cube, it becomes hard and sometimes it gets stuck.

Image 23 - Prototype of 'V' Pillow Cube Screenshot

When the prototype was completed, it was evaluated during a meeting. Because the friction due to the printing technology was hard to overcome, a new prototype was created and shared under the name “V-CUBE PROTOTYPE V2.0”

Image 24 - 'V' Pillow Cube Second Version of the Prototype Screenshot

With the second prototype, the smoothness has been increased and the prototype works well.

In the end, when the last release of the prototype was accomplished, the production can begin.

Image 25 - 'V' Pillow Cube List of prototypes Screenshot

3.1.2.2. RESULTS OF THE PILOTS

Through the described activities, it is possible to understand how the platform can help a toymaker contact a partner who can help him develop a project. In this case Verdes Innovation s. a. has uploaded an idea and transformed it into a real product, with the help of the FabLabs knowledge. It has been simple developing the product, solving issues and obtaining a first prototype rapidly and in an economical way. On the other side, the FabLab had the opportunity to collaborate on an industrial project with someone that is really far from where it is geographically located. Thanks to the platform both partners had the possibility to work in a simpler way, having all the information necessary, starting from the idea and finishing with the product industrial creation.

Moreover, the FabLab has the opportunity to collaborate on industrial projects with international companies based all over Europe, regardless of where they are located. This allows FabLabs to extend their market but also learn new things. For a FabLab involved in the ToyLabs project it is very important to learn how a toymaker thinks and also the standard of quality and expectation of a toymaker. The pilot has helped us understand what it takes to make such a collaboration a successful one.

3.2. OTHER PILOT SCENARIOS

We have seen and analysed the main pilots carried out on the platform. Next, other scenarios proposed during the course of the work package 5 are specified.

These scenarios have been raised with the aim of testing the platform in depth, allowing several market analyses, designs, search partners and prototypes in augmented reality; each of them with the tools provided by the platform. With these scenarios two main aspects have been verified:

- On the one hand, the correct functioning of the platform, its usefulness and its intuitiveness
- On the other hand, it has demonstrated the capacity to reduce the time of creation for new products, the costs, and at the same time improve the processes of creation through the use of new technologies.

This was achieved thanks to the participation of all the stakeholders included in the ToyLabs methodology and platform: the toy companies, FabLabs, Safety Experts, Childhood Experts and Final Users. Each of these stakeholders has participated in a phase of the process of creating new toys.

In total, 21 different scenarios have been carried out, nine for each toy company (V-CUBES and JUEMA). The following is a detail of the scenarios and the level of progress achieved in each of them.

3.2.1.DESCRPTION OF THE SCENARIOS

The following table lists the set of extra scenarios executed on the platform. The first column includes the name of the project, the second the toy company and the third a description of the project idea.

Name of the scenario	Toy Manufacturer in charge	Description
Garden Doll	JUEMA	Simple doll themed on gardening. JUEMA would like to incorporate accessories related to gardening as flowers, hose, carrycot, shovel, etc. Regarding the materials of the wrist, these must be resistant to water, to the corrosion of the earth, etc. since the goal is for children to play with the doll outside.
Surprise Box	JUEMA	The main attraction of this product lies in the surprise effect. It consists of a package that contains a small size doll and an accessory. There will be a total of 10 different models, each doll representing a profession: - Doctor - Teacher - Architect

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plumber - Musician - Cabbie - Dancer - Chef - Journalist - Scientific <p>This doll will help reduce gender stereotypes related to the professions. Children will be able to see many professions represented by women.</p>
Zombie Doll	JUEMA	<p>Zombie doll will be a doll with a zombie style, currently very fashionable on the European continent.</p> <p>To differentiate itself from other brands, this zombie doll manufactured by JUEMA will have the characteristic of incorporating odour effects; in this case, being a zombie, they will be unpleasant odours.</p>
Athletics Doll	JUEMA	<p>Themed doll in the world of sports, more specifically in athletics.</p> <p>This doll will have an average size of 28cm and will be made of flexible plastics such as silicone. The goal is that the joints have a wide range of movements, but always respecting the natural movements of the human body.</p> <p>The doll will be themed with sports clothes, a ribbon in the hair and pigtail.</p> <p>It will be taken into consideration that the doll represents a realistic body size, avoiding creating a too thin doll, so that the children can be represented.</p>
Custom Dolls	JUEMA	<p>New product line by which, customers can buy the basic doll and then, they can also buy different wigs, clothes, accessories, shoes, etc. interchangeable.</p> <p>This will allow the doll to be customizable, encouraging children's creativity, sharing accessories, and role playing.</p> <p>The doll will have a small size, around 12 cm. Accessories such as hair, shoes or backpacks, bags, etc. will be looped through an insertion mechanism.</p> <p>Due to the small size of the components, this doll will focus on an older audience, from 8 years.</p>
Smart Dolls	JUEMA	<p>These dolls will include ICT technology. The goal is to have a small speaker inside, which, connects to the Bluetooth of the smartphone</p>

		<p>and with the use of an app, the doll can communicate with us.</p> <p>In terms of design, the idea is that the doll faithfully represents a girl around 12 years of age.</p> <p>The doll would be made mainly of plastic (polyethylene) and would have a medium size (over 28 cm)</p>
Dolls for Elders	JUEMA	<p>JUEMA wants to create a new line of dolls for adults. In this case, we are thinking of a line focused on older people.</p> <p>This doll is focused on collectors. It will be of classic style and the use of porcelain for arms and legs is valued, while the body of the doll will be made of soft material (fabric, cotton, etc.).</p>
Zero Residue Doll	JUEMA	<p>This project aims to create a doll with the least possible environmental impact. For this, it is intended to make use of recycled and / or biodegradable materials.</p> <p>The doll intended to be designed will be included in the theme of the environment. Our goal is to focus on the "explore nature" trend, detected by the Trend Committee. For this, the idea is to incorporate aspects related to nature.</p> <p>The first idea that we are considering is to incorporate characteristic elements of nature.</p> <p>Shape: The doll will be medium size, 28cm high.</p>
Diverse Dolls	JUEMA	<p>Creation of a new line of dolls based on urban styles and subcultures of the 21st century.</p> <p>Among these styles you will find: rapper, graffiti artists, skaters, hipsters, etc. We are considering making one product for each of the 5 styles.</p> <p>We would like to know if these styles will help normalize and de-heterophilize the different suburban cultures.</p>
Tattoo Masks Doll	JUEMA	<p>This is a customizable doll to which children can add tattoos to it. These tattoos will be included in the doll packaging and they will work by transferring the drawing by its contact with water.</p> <p>The idea is that children customize their dolls.</p>
Electronic 3x3 'V' Pillow Cube	V-CUBES	<p>Modern makeover of the Original 'V' Pillow cube.</p> <p>No more twisting it around here and there, this one has a series of touch buttons that</p>

		automatically move one [or more] illuminated colour[s] in the direction selected.
'V' Polygonal Cube	V-CUBES	A dodecahedron-shaped face-turning twisty puzzle which is very similar to the classic 'V' Cube.
2x2 'V' Pillow Cube Educational	V-CUBES	The perfect cube for beginners, 2x2 'V' Cube is the smallest member of the V-CUBE family. The version of this cube has educational purposes. It is intended for young children and includes the colours of the sides but also the name of the colour in four languages (English, Greek, Spanish, Italian)
'V' Eco Cube	V-CUBES	'V' cube which is made from recyclable materials.
'V' Cube with Folkloric Images	V-CUBES	This new product will be a puzzle cube that will include six images of traditional festivities from different European countries; as for example, the Spanish Flamenco and the German Oktober Fest, among others. The cube will be 3x3.
Treasure Hunt Puzzle	V-CUBES	As the player solves the puzzle, he discovers a story, which will be included in a small book included in the packaging. Each side will form a figure that will allow you to read a different chapter of the book.
Changing Colours Cube	V-CUBES	This cube changes the colour of its sides in order to make it easier or more difficult. This is an adaptive cube, depending on the age of the child and the level of experience it becomes easier or more difficult.
3D Cube	V-CUBES	Each side of the cube has a 3d representation of landscapes, monuments, skylines, etc. This is an advance puzzle cube for older children
'V' Fascicles Cube	V-CUBES	'V' Cube that is purchased by fascicles. Each fascicle includes a piece of the cube and, having them all it can be assembled.
3x3 'V' Flat Cube WHITE	V-CUBES	The classic flat shape of the 3x3 'V' Cube with white sides. This cube is intended for young children in order to paint them and create unique custom cubes. We are still considering with which materials it can be painted, Also, we want to make this toy as educational as possible.
'V' Cubes for the Visually Impaired	V-CUBES	The visually impaired can use their sense of touch to try and solve this challenging puzzle.

Table 1 - List of scenarios

3.2.2. ACTIVITIES EXECUTED IN THE SCENARIOS

In this section the work done with the help of the Platform is detailed, through the creation of the XX scenarios that were previously exposed. The general objective of these scenarios is to make an in-depth use of the platform, with which to reach conclusions that determine its strengths and aspects to improve. The secondary objectives are the following:

- On behalf of Singular Logic, publicize the platform to the partners, detailing the characteristics of the platform and the way in which the different tools are used.
- Present the new features and improvements that have been incorporated into the platform through practical cases.
- Achieve to expand the ecosystem of users and projects in the platform, with the aim that all those people and entities that register in ToyLabs can check the different products and provide suggestions and comments from the perspective of:
 - Childhood Expert for usability, toy attractiveness, category, therapeutic capacity, etc.
 - Safety Expert to check the technical aspects regarding compliance with child safety regulations.
 - FabLabs for the production of prototypes, both virtual and printed with the latest technologies.
 - Final Users, which will contribute their vision as potential buyers of those products that are developed on the platform.
- Detect possible bugs in the platform, for its quick correction and create a fully functional, updated and reliable platform.

In order to make scenarios as close as possible to the actual development of a new product, not all scenarios have reached the same level of progress. The level of progress is determined by different factors:

The process of creating a new product advances from the creation of the concept until reaching a product ready for production. The process of creating a new product, within the platform, is done in five fundamental steps. Next, the level of development that was reached for each scenario is shown.

Selection of the scenarios to execute.

The selection of the scenarios was jointly made by the entire project consortium. Each organization proposed a list of possible scenarios, divided between JUEMA and V-CUBES. These scenarios should be adapted to their specific needs and characteristics (line of products, materials, etc.), and, after

come consideration, the most interesting ones were selected, for their implementation through the platform.

Incorporation of scenarios on the platform

Once the scenarios that would be executed were defined, the first phase of the creation of the products began. Both JUEMA and V-CUBES introduced the selected scenarios in the platform, creating their first concepts, in which a first sketch of the type of product was provided, a description of the needs and characteristics of the toy they were beginning to create, the audience to which would be directed (age range), etc.

This phase was applied to all scenarios.

Images 26 y 27 - Scenarios executed by JUEMA and V-CUBES

Execution of the market analysis

The next phase in the process of creating a new product is based on the execution of a market analysis, through which you can observe the trends and the public opinion on specific topics, introduced on the platform through the use of keywords,

These market analyses were carried out in all scenarios, with the aim of checking which were the most interesting and selecting them to continue with the design process.

SmartDolls market analysis

Overview

Electronic 3x3 'V' Pillow Cube market analysis

Overview

3x3 'V' Flat Cube WHITE market analysis 2

Overview

Athletics doll market analysis

Overview

Image 28- Scenarios Market and Trend Analysis executions

Out of a total of 20 scenarios, a total of 15 have been selected. The selected scenarios are those that presented the most interesting concepts after carrying out the analysis. In those scenarios in which there are no relevant trends related to the type of toy, the theme, the action, etc., it has been decided not to continue developing the product; since with the analysis we can assume that there will not

be a good acceptance in the market regarding that toy. Here are four examples of the analyses performed:

Creation of product design

The next phase was the design of the 15 products whose results in the trend analysis were favourable. In this phase the design was defined, Augmented Reality models were created, and the following collaborations were established:

- Collaboration with FabLabs that are members of the consortium in order to define the form that the product and its physical characteristics would have.
- Collaboration with Childhood Experts: based on providing feedback on their impressions of the product being designed, suggesting changes in the form, incorporation of new features, etc. that make the product more attractive to end users.
- Collaboration with Safety Experts: in order to verify that the design complies with European regulations and regulations regarding the safety of children's products.
- Collaboration of Final Users: which have been able to contribute their perspective on the product, commenting on the aspects they like and those that they do not, their preferences, etc.

Image 29 - 'V' Cubes for the Visually Impaired Scenario concept and Feedbacks

This phase in the creation of new products has also helped to discern which scenarios present a greater chance of success and which should be discarded for security reasons, viability of their production, or interest of the end users, due to the feedback provided by the different stakeholders listed.

With the creation of the design, and after gathering the necessary feedback from the stakeholders involved in this new ToyLabs Methodology, it has been possible to obtain a final design, on which the creation of a first prototype is based. The physical prototype is developed in the facilities of the FabLabs, who have state-of-the-art technology, with the close collaboration of the toy company, who will supervise the development of the physical prototypes.

Prototypes creation phase

Some of these proposed scenarios have reached the last phase of the ToyLabs methodology, by which a final prototype is obtained, developed thanks to the technology of the dependencies of the FabLabs. The prototypes are obtained through the use of 3D printing machines.

In the figure below, the case of the "Tattoo Mask Doll" scenario is presented, whose objective was to obtain a mould of a mask that would cover the head of the wrist, leaving the eyes and lips uncovered, in order to paint them effectively, fast and accurately.

Image 30 - Doll Mask scenario Prototype

Image 31 - Doll Mask Prototype Obtained

3.3. EXPLOTATION CAPABILITY OF THE PLATFORM

3.3.1. CURRENT STATUS OF THE PLATFORM

The ToyLabs Platform is in the stage of launching, after its bugs have been solved, and the benefit of its use have been demonstrated. At the moment, the platform is in continuous growth of users. Currently, users are distributed according to the following table:

Number and expertise of users of ToyLabs Platform	
Administrators	2
Manufacturers	20
FabLabs	43
Child Experts	19
Safetuy Experts	6
End users	133
TOTAL USERS	223

Table 2 - Number and expertise of users of ToyLabs Platform

In addition to an increasing number of users on the platform, the number of interactions, comments, analysis, concepts, etc. demonstrate a continued use of different tools and options. The following table shows the interactions on the platform:

Number of uses and Interactions within the Platform	
Number of products created	67
Number of designs achieved	63
Number of prototypes achieved	35
Number of collaborations created	53
Number of AR Models Created	39
Number of negotiation messages	63
Number of feedback messages	17

Table 3 - Number of uses and interactions within the Platform

3.3.2. PARTNERS EXPLOITATION OF THE PLATFORM

At point 2.4. “Exploitation and Sustainability strategies for single partners” of Deliverable 7.5. “Exploitation Report, Updated plan and First Release of business innovation” an exhaustive analysis of the exploitation capacity of each partner is made for each of the results obtained in the ToyLabs project. The following are all the specific exploitable aspects of the ToyLabs Platform. It has been considered necessary to carry out a specific analysis of the exploitation of the Platform, following the previous experience with the pilots, and with a perspective focused on maximizing the benefits detected during the course of the pilots.

FABLABS (LECCE & ROMANIA) exploitation of the Platform

FabLabs, after the toy companies, will be the organisations that can best exploit the results of the platform, due to their nature: offer access to the equipment they have. The FabLabs will find in the Platform a new market, with a multitude of toy companies, with which they can collaborate and offer their services.

The ToyLabs Platform will be the meeting point between companies that require high technology services and FabLabs that will make their equipment available for the companies in order to develop prototypes with innovative technologies and materials, 3D designs and Augmented Reality designs, among other services.

MANUFACTURERS (V-CUBES & JUEMA) exploitation of the Platform

The ToyLabs project was born aiming to help SMEs in the toy sector reduce their costs and production times of new products, as well as reduce the rates of failure of their products.

The ToyLabs Platform fulfils those objectives. The companies of the consortium now have a space developed specifically to help them obtain new products, with specific tools and, above all, with an ecosystem of institutions and people that have the ability to be involved in all phases of creation of new products.

As demonstrated during WP5, the benefits of using the platform are already evident (KPIs) and, in addition, will increase steadily over time, along with the increase of subscribed organizations.

AIJU exploitation of the Platform

AIJU will focus on the exploitation of the platform through training sessions of its users belonging on the different organisations that are members of the

platform. This training will mean the increase of the platform's users. With the pilots, AIJU has developed a new channel for Safety Studies of children product's services.

NTUA exploitation of the Platform

NTUA, being an academic institution, will focus on the exploitation of the knowledge obtained during the ToyLabs project. Regarding the Platform, they will carry out dissemination and training activities.

SINGULAR LOGIC exploitation of the Platform

SINGULAR LOGIC will focus its exploitation effort of the Platform through maintenance and fine tuning of the pilot prototype but also through extension of the ToyLabs framework adoption from other development teams within the company.

3.3.3. MARKET SITUATION

Market situation analysis is presented on detail in D7.5 "Exploitation Report, Updated plan and First Release of Business Innovation".

The toy sector has a big dependence on customer need satisfaction. As soon as kid's wishes change, the toy sector must be flexible to develop new products that meet these desires. That is the reason that toy industry spends time and money on market analysis, protection of intellectual property and R&D. The fact that 60% of toys on the market are new is a key figure.

as According to TIE numbers in 2011, 90% of toy companies put new products on market, compared with other industry sectors (less than 40%).

Focusing on traditional games and toys, the size of the segment is about 1/3 of the global market as this was examined by Euromonitor. A very important fact is that the estimated annual growth in this segment reaches 4% which proves the potential and the positive prospects of the specific market that ToyLabs is addressed to.

In 2011, traditional games and toys sales reached 58 billion €. Traditional toys and games market declined between 2002 and 2005. The global market of toys and games (including both traditional toys and electronic games) already has a huge size as well as an impressive growth rate, despite the economic crisis. While these statistics do not refer to the exact market for ToyLabs (since they also include games/ non-traditional toys), they highlight the size, value and prospects of the broader market. There is an impressive growth rate of near 4%

in the size of the global Toys and Games market since 2013 accelerating global growth”. The market was estimated at 175 billion USD for 2015.

A large proportion of manufacturing takes place in China, while activities like research and development (R&D), testing, design and marketing are carried out in European countries with a movement of 5.6 billion €.

Considering potential stakeholders the platform can have, there is a first overview that depends on the profile of each stakeholder:

TOYMAKERS

Officially, we need to take in account that in Europe there are Almost 5,000 toy companies, of which 99% are SMEs (between 0 and 249 employees).

Image 32 Europe Toy industry figures. Source: <https://www.toyindustries.eu/>

Figures from this 99% of SMEs:

- 84% between 0-9 employees
- 14% between 10-49 employees

This project is part of the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No [732559].

Table 4 Manufacture of games and toys: number of employees, breakdown by country. Source: EUROSTAT SBS (2013)

We also need to consider that the Toy sector is a creative industry that can include a lot of companies that are not officially considered as toymakers: inventors, sculptors, designers, freelancers, retailers, toy import companies, gift shops, companies dedicated to children's products and childcare, all of which can also be included on the potential users of platform.

FABLABS

A Fab Lab is a technical prototyping platform for innovation and invention, providing stimulus for local entrepreneurship. This new business model is growing quickly.

FABLAB is a developer profile in platform, as they bring to toymakers new technologies needed to create toys.

Moreover, FABLABS can be considered in TOYLABS as a TOYMAKERS as they have very creative ideas even though they have little knowledge about the Toy Development Process.

From **FABLABS.IO** it can be seen that in Europe 659 FabLabs exist:

Austria 9
 Belgium 21
 Bulgaria 1
 Croatia 1
 Cyprus 1
 Czech Republic 3
 Denmark 7
 Finland 7
 France 158
 Germany 48
 Greece 3
 Iceland 8
 Ireland 5
 Italy 137
 Latvia 2
 Lithuania 2
 Luxembourg 2
 Malta 1
 Netherlands 33
 Norway 5
 Poland 13
 Portugal 20
 Romania 1
 Russia 31
 Serbia 4

Slovakia 3
Slovenia 3
Spain 52
Sweden 2
Switzerland 18
Turkey 10
Ukraine 6
United Kingdom 42

Following that, the Services and Technologies that FABLABS can offer to the Toy Sector are presented:

3D printing
Laser cut
Vinyl cutting
CNC Milling
Precision milling
Circuit production
3D Scanning
Acrylic Bending Machine
Drone
Furnace
Hot String
Infrared oven
Knitting machine
Lathing
Pottery Wheel
Sewing machine
Soldering Station
Thermostatic Basin
Transfer press
Vacuum Forming
Virtual Reality
Welding Machine

CHILDREN'S ENVIRONMENT

In the toy sector target group are rapidly changing. We always consider that Toys are for Children, but trends evolve to the elderly increasingly the focus of development for products and toys.

We will focus the data to the children's target audience. Using Eurostat as a reference (http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database?node_code=proj), the European toy market is the largest in the world covering demands close to 64 M EU children.

GEO/TIME	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
European Union (current composition)	62 483.665	62 687.140	62 901.325	63 044.112	63 135.110	63 163.863	63 289.263	63 531.548	63 765.851	63 923.308
European Union (before the accession of Croatia)	61 960.870	62 170.906	62 390.365	62 537.683	62 632.819	62 663.813	62 791.488	63 035.389	63 274.652	63 438.439
Euro area (19 countries)	41 127.695	41 292.696	41 341.036	41 325.687	41 286.469	41 181.915	41 162.379	41 199.395	41 255.638	41 239.376
Euro area (18 countries)	40 753.352	40 926.141	40 981.289	40 976.105	40 943.388	40 841.732	40 822.685	40 857.705	40 911.486	40 894.774
Belgium	1 433.083	1 450.133	1 465.512	1 496.976	1 511.640	1 522.116	1 530.767	1 542.249	1 553.746	1 556.723
Bulgaria	772 255	775 319	787 663	792 296	795 530	797 844	801 796	808 589	811 782	811 832
Czech Republic	1 149 185	1 183 209	1 216 293	1 250 027	1 270 763	1 289 594	1 305 419	1 324 733	1 343 663	1 360 265
Denmark	796 164	794 412	790 691	788 639	781 981	773 916	766 148	761 825	760 695	761 400
Germany (until 1990 former territory of the FRG)	8 891 543	8 767 908	8 623 005	8 480 967	8 392 864	8 338 422	8 339 272	8 418 433	8 635 857	8 810 951
Germany including former GDR	8 891 543	8 767 908	8 623 005	8 480 967	8 392 864	8 338 422	8 339 272	8 418 433	8 635 857	8 810 951
Estonia	158 150	161 070	164 370	168 060	170 476	171 165	171 821	172 771	174 446	175 304
Ireland	741 744	762 596	779 937	794 493	805 076	811 490	814 467	815 981	815 779	816 791
Greece	1 288 949	1 294 694	1 302 397	1 304 249	1 303 086	1 293 505	1 278 590	1 258 193	1 239 547	1 237 685
Spain	5 418 606	5 575 864	5 665 830	5 735 884	5 778 089	5 769 983	5 725 523	5 693 433	5 646 139	5 592 688
France	9 529 991	9 586 156	9 644 974	9 694 472	9 740 417	9 738 313	9 735 680	9 819 928	9 810 016	9 776 305
France (metropolitan)	9 157 013	9 213 732	9 274 293	9 327 133	9 380 380	9 384 358	#VALOR!	#VALOR!	#VALOR!	#VALOR!
Croatia	522 795	516 234	510 960	506 429	502 291	500 050	497 775	496 159	491 199	484 869
Italy	6 603 117	6 660 954	6 688 355	6 687 026	6 659 958	6 662 684	6 729 506	6 664 534	6 572 898	6 469 732
Cyprus	107 543	107 699	108 734	110 118	112 473	113 157	111 909	111 954	112 735	112 990
Latvia	239 576	243 349	244 027	241 749	240 056	239 119	240 360	243 222	245 569	248 470
Lithuania	374 343	366 555	359 747	349 582	343 081	340 183	339 694	341 690	344 152	344 602
Luxembourg	69 725	70 103	70 523	71 560	71 328	72 300	73 575	74 754	76 232	77 065
Hungary	1 169 165	1 163 520	1 162 416	1 157 134	1 147 873	1 141 545	1 136 835	1 135 651	1 136 018	1 136 641
Malta	50 053	49 241	48 529	47 874	47 830	48 017	48 913	50 245	51 426	52 707
Netherlands	2 344 167	2 336 788	2 330 414	2 317 113	2 297 650	2 266 859	2 236 117	2 213 216	2 190 832	2 179 570
Austria	989 817	978 549	969 045	964 539	963 823	964 373	968 898	975 105	994 875	1 008 100
Poland	4 516 938	4 502 549	4 555 133	4 586 532	4 590 278	4 601 713	4 603 245	4 626 093	4 647 166	4 680 852
Portugal	1 311 576	1 302 458	1 287 575	1 262 625	1 236 923	1 209 006	1 184 471	1 159 424	1 139 751	1 124 424
Romania	2 601 948	2 554 584	2 544 151	2 539 091	2 525 495	2 478 243	2 444 548	2 444 535	2 440 250	2 434 295
Slovenia	221 135	225 461	229 748	234 293	238 881	242 662	245 874	248 948	252 061	253 920
Slovakia	655 333	653 444	656 010	656 595	661 296	662 868	667 333	672 754	678 048	683 857
Finland	699 244	699 674	702 304	707 512	711 522	715 793	719 609	722 561	721 619	717 492
Sweden	1 196 227	1 216 204	1 242 005	1 269 556	1 294 060	1 319 240	1 348 259	1 373 947	1 398 027	1 428 059
United Kingdom	8 631 293	8 688 413	8 750 977	8 828 721	8 940 370	9 078 803	9 222 859	9 360 621	9 481 413	9 585 719
European Economic Area (EU28 - current composition, plus IS, LI, NO)	63 259 396	63 466 055	63 685 123	63 833 370	63 927 572	63 960 436	64 090 670	64 337 997	64 574 381	64 733 936
European Economic Area (EU27 - before the accession of Croatia, plus IS, LI, NO)	62 736 601	62 949 821	63 174 163	63 326 941	63 425 281	63 460 386	63 592 895	63 841 838	64 083 182	64 249 067
European Free Trade Association	1 696 031	1 701 906	1 710 057	1 726 356	1 736 617	1 747 231	1 767 123	1 787 499	1 805 571	1 823 723
Iceland	52 221	52 995	53 211	53 428	53 431	53 551	53 941	54 285	53 993	53 964
Liechtenstein	4 646	4 584	4 565	4 519	4 515	4 479	4 451	4 462	4 483	4 486
Norway	718 864	721 336	726 022	731 311	734 516	738 543	743 015	747 702	750 054	752 178
Switzerland	920 300	922 991	926 259	937 098	944 155	950 658	965 716	981 050	997 041	1 013 095
Montenegro	95 300	94 711	94 854	93 755	92 893	92 052	91 178	90 381	89 820	89 879
Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, the	289 115	283 980	281 409	279 857	278 275	276 038	274 621	275 066	274 651	274 329
Albania	#VALOR!	#VALOR!	#VALOR!	#VALOR!	#VALOR!	#VALOR!	412 474	402 223	386 841	401 633

Table 5 Number of children in EUROPE (More than 60 million)

The TOYLABS methodology wants to also evolve Childhood experts as creators on new products. Concepts like STEM or STEAM are introduced in schools. Teachers are more and more implicated on it, thanks to European calls like Erasmus +

(https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/opportunities/calls_en)

In the following table, the number of teachers per country in Europe is shown according to Eurostat:

	2013	2014	2015	2016
European Union (current com	2,015,082 ^(a)	2,065,578 ^(a)	2,164,627	:
Belgium	68,576 ^(a)	68,826 ^(a)	69,681	70,530
Bulgaria	14,388	14,596	14,769	14,876
Czech Republic	25,979	27,339	28,192	29,107
Denmark	:	43,537	:	:(^{d)}
Germany (until 1990 former t	233,046	232,750	235,571	238,361
Estonia	6,548	6,771	7,049	7,352
Ireland	32,175	32,828	33,613	34,576
Greece	66,735	66,551	66,755	69,716
Spain	220,323	226,066	228,299	233,065
France	229,471	228,648	235,659	228,644
Croatia	:(^{d)}	:	11,849	12,033
Italy	237,735	237,214	237,483	254,572
Cyprus	3,977	3,967	4,513	4,597
Latvia	10,221	10,338	10,537	10,619
Lithuania	8,642	8,441	8,401	8,330
Luxembourg	4,330	4,338	4,247	4,411
Hungary	37,054 ^(a)	34,955	36,029	36,632
Malta	1,702	1,799	1,825	1,933
Netherlands	107,439	104,815	103,930	101,643
Austria	30,566	30,533	30,972	31,933
Poland	211,238	211,201	219,826	229,490
Portugal	54,222	50,276	49,355	50,001
Romania	50,626	50,857	50,098	48,591
Slovenia	6,468	6,666	6,836	8,664
Slovakia	14,050	14,030	14,182	14,447
Finland	26,402	26,385	26,150	26,996
Sweden	62,105	63,467	65,459	66,918
United Kingdom	250,693	258,047	320,014 ^(a)	313,649
Iceland	3,001	2,991	2,999	3,058
Liechtenstein	261	246	252	260
Norway	47,444	48,124	48,583	50,979
Switzerland	46,306	47,889	47,356	49,167
Former Yugoslav Republic of	7,060	7,137	7,554	7,357
Serbia	:	18,701	18,318	18,875
Turkey	282,043	288,444	:	302,961

Table 6 . Number of teachers in EUROPE (More than 60 million)

3.3.4. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Future perspectives of the TOYLABS platform are mainly presented in detail in D7.5 “Exploitation Report, Updated plan and First Release of Business Innovation”.

Considering previous figures, the most important point to highlight is that realistic scenarios that allow generating a plan in the short / medium term that will allow the platform to grow and be sustainable for 6 years have been defined.

Four years into the future, the platform is planned to have covered the initial investment and found a company that can manage the platform autonomously.

For this, the scenarios have defined the potential costs of the platform and an analysis of possible income determined by the progressive increase of users of different profiles.

While these objectives are reached, AIJU as the coordinator will take over the management of the platform in the same way that SINGULAR LOGIC will take charge of the maintenance and management.

AIJU has a special interest in the platform aiming at its continuous growth, since as a non-profit research organization focused on the toy sector its main objective is by definition to help small businesses innovate and improve their position in the market.

3.4. EVALUATION OF THE PLATFORM AND CAPABILITY

This section details the evaluation carried out during the pilots' process.

This evaluation has been based on three main aspects:

- The first was the detection of errors in the technical and conceptual functioning of the platform, which has been thoroughly tested during the 5 months of WP5.
- The second evaluation method has been the completion by JUEMA and V-CUBES of the questionnaires developed for comparing the methodology and platform of ToyLabs with their traditional methods of creating new products. In these questionnaires, general qualitative information has been collected from the pilots.
- Finally, the last aspect for the evaluation of the effectiveness of the results of the project has been in the KPIs, with which we have obtained quantitative data regarding the reductions of time, costs, etc. which entails the use of the platform.

3.4.1. DETECTION OF BUGS AND RESOLUTIONS

The following list resumes all the bugs detected in the Platform. The information about the error and the solutions applied are detailed:

Increase the maximum size of the uploaded files to the platform.

During the piloting, different stakeholders, FabLabs and Manufacturers, had to interchange documents regarding the 3D modelling, pictures and text documents for the collaboration in the process of creating a new product.

The ToyLabs platform allows attachments to messages between users. The limit is 8 files.

Image 32 - Files size issues in the Platform

While making use of this tool, FabLab Romania detected that the maximum size was 2mb per file. This size was insufficient for uploading heavy files of 3D modelling, pictures or other type of files.

Therefore, it was reported to SINGULAR LOGIC, who solved the problem by increasing the maximum size of files to 32mb.

Error when creating an organisation with final user account

One of the first steps of the piloting, was to sign in to the platform and create an organisation profile.

Image 33 - Creation of an organization Section Screenshot

When the users registered on the platform, they tried to create the organisations they represented. This was impossible due to an error when pressing the Validation button:

Once this bug was detected, AIJU contacted SINGULAR LOGIC to inform them of the situation. After analysing the bug, SINGULAR LOGIC detected that the problem was based on the type of user with whom the personal account had been created. On the platform, users can register as: safety expert, manufacturer, FabLab and end user. The users who register as end users should not have the ability to create organisations, since these users are parents and end users of the products and not members of any organisation related to toys development. The option to create an organisation was shown to the end users and, when the "create" button was pressed, an error appeared:

When checking the type of users who had tried to register their organisation, SINGULAR LOGIC realized that all of them were registered as end users.

To correct the problem, the user type was specified for each person and the option to create the organisation on the platform was blocked to those people who registered as end users.


```

Whoops, looks like something went wrong.

[1] ErrorException
Trying to get property of non-object

in ProfileController.php (line 172)

at HandleExceptions->handleError(0, 'Trying to get property of non-object', 'http://www.toylabs.es/01app/Http/Controllers/ProfileController.php', 172, array('request' => object(Request), 'input' => array('token' => '820r784ub06wUy1T0N0qNwCbyP-hF0d4', 'name' => 'AIJU', 'legal_name' => 'Technological Institute for children's product & leisure', 'legal_form' => 'FReelancer', 'description' => null, 'address' => 'Avenida de la Industria, 23 03440 Ibi (Alicante) España', 'postal_code' => '03440', 'city' => 'Ibi', 'country_id' => '200', 'zip_code' => null, 'phone' => '+34 96 509 44 79', 'fax' => '+34 96 509 44 90', 'website_url' => null, 'instagram' => null, 'facebook' => null, 'twitter' => null, 'id' => '0', 'facilities' => [], 'services' => [], 'awards' => [], 'certifications' => [], 'owner_id' => 35, 'id' => '0', 'user' => object(User)))
in ProfileController.php (line 172)

at ProfileController->saveOrganizationProfile(object(Request))

at call_user_func_array(array(object(ProfileController), 'saveOrganizationProfile'), array(object(Request)))
in Controller.php (line 55)

at Controller->callAction('saveOrganizationProfile', array(object(Request)))
in ControllerDispatcher.php (line 44)

at ControllerDispatcher->dispatch(object(Route), object(ProfileController), 'saveOrganizationProfile')
in Route.php (line 203)

at Route->runController()
in Route.php (line 160)

at Route->run()
in Router.php (line 574)

at Router->illuminateRouting(closure): object(Request)
in Pipeline.php (line 33)

at Pipeline->illuminateRouting(closure): object(Request)
in SubstituteBindings.php (line 41)

at SubstituteBindings->handle(object(Request), object(Closure))
in Pipeline.php (line 148)

at Pipeline->illuminatePipeline(closure): object(Request)
in Pipeline.php (line 53)

at Pipeline->illuminateRouting(closure): object(Request)

```

Image 34 - Error when creating the organization in the Platform Screenshot

Problems with the link to the webpage of the institution

When the children's experts were involved in the project, they were asked by the consortium to register their institutions on the platform.

Image 35 - Link to the Organization Website Screenshot

In the registration screen, there is the possibility of inserting a link to the web page of the institution. The childhood experts reported an error in which, when clicking on the link, it broke before opening the webpage.

The problem was solved as soon as possible, from SINGULAR LOGIC who worked on this issue and solved the bug in less than 48 hours.

Impossibility of updating the analysis of the Social Analytics & Market Trends Analysis Tool

This tool offers the possibility of updating an existing analysis, with more keywords or changing the period of time of the study. A problem with this updating system was detected when manufacturers tried to upload the analysis and the platform broke.

Image 36 - Error in the Market Trend Analysis Tool

This error has been solved, now it includes two buttons: “update” which updates the previous analysis, and “save as copy” which saves it as a placeholder.

Impossibility to add comments in the visualisations of the Social Analytics & Market Trends Analysis Tool

This tool includes a section for comments, in which the reflections of the results of the analysis can be annotated.

Image 37 - Error when adding comments in the results of the analysis

The issue was that when users wanted to save the comments, the platform did not upload them to the server, eliminating directly the entered text.

About page was empty of information

The about page is important because it collects the most important information regarding the objective of the ToyLabs project and the Platform. The objectives and impact of the use of the platform in the different stakeholders to which the project is directed are listed.

As this page was empty, the consortium worked in the development of the text and in the implementation of it into the platform.

Image 38 - About ToyLabs Screenshot

3.4.2. TOYLABS PILOTING AND EVALUATION SHEETS

This section is intimately related to chapter 4, "Evaluation Methodology" of the deliverable 5.1 "Pilots Readiness Documentation". In this section, the variables and the structure of the questionnaires with which the pilots have been evaluated in this last phase of the work package 5 were detailed.

As defined in D5.1, these questionnaires were completed by the two consortium manufacturers (V-CUBES and JUEMA), due to their continued participation from the beginning of the pilots (with the first phases of creation of a product) until the end of them (when they have obtained the physical prototypes, printed by the FabLabs, based on the methodology and the ToyLabs platform).

These questionnaires have been completed through the Google Forms tool, since Internet use is much faster and more efficient (with which the questionnaires can be completed at any time, from any place with a connection to the network) and, in addition, the results are obtained instantaneously.

The following three tables compile the answers obtained in each of the three questionnaires prepared for each phase of the creation process: conceptualization, design and development.

EVAUATION RESULTS OF THE CONCEPTUALIZATION PHASE	
Questions	Answers
Which pilot are you evaluating?	Mechanical Puzzle Toys Pilot Dolls & Accessories Pilot
About the Overall Platform	
How is the overall operation of the platform? System functioning, speed of the responses, bugs, etc. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with an eight in the Likert Scale.
How is the overall usability of the platform? Learning curve of the platform, ease of learning, etc. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	One manufacturer evaluated It with a seven and the other with an eight in the Likert Scale.
How is the overall practicality of the platform? Simplicity and accessibility of all the functions as well as the time necessary to carry out the tasks. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with an eight in the Likert Scale.
Which is the overall added value of the platform? The advantages of the use of the platform against other dynamics and tools of creation of a new product. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with an eight in the Likert Scale.
About the piloting	
Being 1 no cooperation at all, and 10 full cooperation during the conceptualization, which has been the cooperation level during the conceptualization scenario?	One manufacturer evaluated It with a seven and the other with an eight in the Likert Scale.
Being 1 not fulfilment of times at all and 10 complete fulfilment of times during the conceptualization, which has been the level of fulfilment of times of the conceptualization scenario?	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with a seven in the Likert Scale.
How has been the functioning of the “dashboard” section? The “dashboard” should be easy to use and it must provide general information about the state of current projects as well as the	One manufacturer evaluated It with an eight and the other with a nine in the Likert Scale.

possibility of creating a new project. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	
How has been the functioning of “ToyLabs Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component”? Evaluate the operation of this component. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	One manufacturer evaluated It with a six and the other with an eight in the Likert Scale.
Quantitative variables for the conceptualization phase	
Hours dedicated for the process of conceptualization of a new toy with the traditional methodology of the SME’s:	Manufacturer 1: maybe 20 hours
	Manufacturer 2: I don’t know
Hours dedicated for the process of conceptualization of a new toy with the ToyLabs methodology:	Manufacturer 1: 10 hours
	Manufacturer 2: 20 hours
Cost of the research of the toy trends for the conceptualization of the product by using traditional methodologies of the SME’s:	Both manufacturers choose “ I do not know ” option for this question.
Cost of the research of the toy trends for the conceptualization of the product by using ToyLabs methodologies:	Both manufacturers choose “ about free ” option for this question.
Level of accuracy in the search of the trends using traditional methodologies of the SME’s in the search of market trends (1 there is not accuracy at all, 10 there is completely accuracy):	One manufacturer evaluated It with a six and the other with a seven in the Likert Scale.
Cost of the process of conceptualization using the traditional methodologies of the SME’s:	Both manufacturers choose “ I do not know ” option for this question.
Cost of the process of conceptualization using the ToyLabs methodologies:	Both manufacturers choose “ about free ” option for this question.

Table 7 - Evaluation Results of the Conceptualization Phase

EVAUATION RESULTS OF THE DESIGN PHASE	
Questions	Answers
Which pilot are you evaluating?	Mechanical Puzzle Toys Pilot
	Dolls & Accessories Pilot
About the Platform	
How is the overall operation of the platform? System functioning, speed of the responses, bugs, etc. (evaluate	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with an eight in the Likert Scale.

from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	
How is the overall practicality of the platform? Simplicity and accessibility of all the functions as well as the time necessary to carry out the tasks. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	One manufacturer evaluated It with a seven and the other with an eight in the Likert Scale.
Which is the overall added value of the platform? The advantages of the use of the platform against other dynamics and tools of creation of a new product. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	One manufacturer evaluated It with a seven and the other with an eight in the Likert Scale.
About the piloting	
Being 1 no cooperation at all, and 10 full cooperation during the design, which has been the cooperation level during the design scenario?	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with a seven in the Likert Scale.
Being 1 not fulfilment of times at all and 10 complete fulfilment of times during the design, which has been the level of fulfilment of times of the design phase?	One manufacturer evaluated It with a seven and the other with an eight in the Likert Scale.
How has been the functioning of the “Partner Matching & Selection Mechanism” section?	One manufacturer evaluated It with a seven and the other with an eight in the Likert Scale.
How has been the functioning of the “Augmented Reality Engine” section?	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with a seven in the Likert Scale.
How effective have been the Copyrights security systems?	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with a ten in the Likert Scale.
Quantitative variables for the design phase	
Hours dedicated for the process of conceptualization of a new toy with the traditional methodology of the SME's:	Manufacturer 1: maybe 20 hours
	Manufacturer 2: maybe 50 hours
Hours dedicated for the process of design of a new toy with the ToyLabs methodology:	Manufacturer 1: 10 hours
	Manufacturer 2: 20 hours
Cost of the process of design using the traditional methodologies of the SME's:	Both manufacturers choose “ I do not know ” option for this question.
Cost of the process of design using the ToyLabs methodologies:	Both manufacturers choose “ about free ” option for this question.

Table 8 - Evaluation Results of the Design Phase

EVAUATION RESULTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT PHASE	
Questions	Answers
Which pilot are you evaluating?	Mechanical Puzzle Toys Pilot Dolls & Accessories Pilot
About the Platform	
How is the overall operation of the platform? System functioning, speed of the responses, bugs, etc. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with an eight in the Likert Scale.
How is the overall practicality of the platform? Simplicity and accessibility of all the functions as well as the time necessary to carry out the tasks. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	One manufacturer evaluated It with an eight and the other with a nine in the Likert Scale.
Which is the overall added value of the platform? The advantages of the use of the platform against other dynamics and tools of creation of a new product. (evaluate from 1 to 10; being 1 really bad and 10 really good)	One manufacturer evaluated It with an eight and the other with a nine in the Likert Scale.
About the piloting	
Being 1 no cooperation at all, and 10 full cooperation during the development phase, which has been the cooperation level during the development phase?	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with a seven in the Likert Scale.
Being 1 not fulfilment of times at all and 10 complete fulfilment of times during the development, which has been the level of fulfilment of times of the development phase?	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with an eight in the Likert Scale.
How has been the functioning of the “Partner Matching & Selection Mechanism” section?	One manufacturer evaluated It with a seven and the other with an eight in the Likert Scale.
How has been the functioning of the “End Users Interface” section?	Both of the manufacturers evaluated with a seven in the Likert Scale.
How is the quality of the prototype developed during the pilot?	One manufacturer evaluated It with a six and the other with an eight in the Likert Scale.
How much innovation have you appreciated in the process of developing the prototype?	One manufacturer evaluated It with a seven and the other with an eight in the Likert Scale.
Which is the overall acceptance level of the prototype?	One manufacturer evaluated It with a six and the other with a nine in the Likert Scale.

Table 9 - Evaluation Results of the Development Phase

With all this information gathered, it is possible to elaborate conclusive considerations on the success of the pilots and the level of acceptance, usability and added value of the platform, according to the opinion of the companies in the toy sector. These conclusions are listed below:

- The operation of the platform has been evaluated by toy companies with eight out of ten, a high score.
- In addition, the companies consider that the platform has a high added value, since its evaluation in this regard has been of an average of eight, with scores between seven and nine, out of ten.
- In this qualitative evaluation, we have also seen that the different tools provided by the Platform with regards to executing the creation of new pilots have been well received by the experts. The evaluations have been the following:
 - The "ToyLabs Market Analytics and Trends Analysis" tool, was evaluated by the toy companies with an average of seven out of ten.
 - The tool "Partner Matching & Selection Mechanism" tool, was evaluated by the toy companies with an average of seven and a half out of ten.
 - The "Augmented Reality Engine" tool, was evaluated by the toy companies with seven out of ten.
- Regarding the times devoted to the different phases, we can see how they have been reduced with the use of the platform.
 - In the conceptualization phase, times have been reduced from 20 hours to 10 hours.
 - In the design phase, times have been reduced from an average of 35 hours to 15 hours.
- Regarding the prototyping phase, this has been satisfactory, with an eight regarding the innovation in the process and a seven in the level of acceptance.

3.4.3. KPIS AND MAIN BENEFITS

Having collected qualitative information directly from the final users of the project and quantitative information on the use of the platform, the table below shows the main KPIs of the platform. This table is also found in D5.2., However, in this case, in addition to the objectives set, the achievements are also shown (last column).

It is important to mention that, due to the collaborative nature of the platform, many of the proposed KPIs will be achieved progressively, as more users (manufacturers, FabLabs, Safety Experts, Childhood Experts and Final Users)

register and become familiar with the ToyLabs Platform. In the D.7.5 "Exploitation Report, Updated Plan and First Release of Business Innovation", the exploitation and use plan of the Platform for the next years is detailed.

For now, this table details those objectives achieved after the five months of activity of the Pilots:

#	Performance Indicator	Related Stakeholders	QUANTIFICATION	
			OBJECTIVE	ACHIEVEMENT
1	Time-to-market	Manufacturer	50% reduction	In the questionnaires, companies have evaluated a reduction of time in all phases of creation of new products by 50%.
1.1	Market analysis time	Manufacturer	20-40% reduction	With the use of the platform's market analysis tool, market analysis times are reduced as the entire process is automated by using keywords and parameters.
1.2	Time to design new product	Manufacturer	5-10% reduction	Traditionally companies work with sculptors, this process was full of imperfections because it is a manual labor. Computer 3D Design reduced errors by 5 to 10%, depending on complexity of the model.
1.3	Time to construct the prototype	Manufacturer	5-15% reduction	Traditional process to build a prototype includes sculpture work. Sculptors work slower than 3D Printers. Moving on into the future, this percentage will

				increase to 30 or 40% when 3 or 4 restylings from the original designs will be needed.
1.4	Time to find a collaborator	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts	10-30% reduction	With the "Partner Matching" tool, the manufacturer can quickly find the partner organizations he needs, by specifying the technology and tasks he desires. The reduction in time can be greater than previously estimated (5-15%)
1.5	Inquiry/feedback response time	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts	Around 30% reduction	Platform collaboration tools enable users to open a quicker channel. The ability to use the Augmented Reality Module improved communication between Experts and Designers/Toymakers.
1.6	Time for data exchange	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts	Around 30% reduction	As the platform supports several data Exchange systems, all users (manufacturers, fablabs, experts etc.) understand from the beginning the rules related to the standards used and, using Platform Tools are able to work directly.
1.7	Number of iterations in the quoting process	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts	Increased by 1-3	Continuous iterations between FabLabs, Manufacturers and Experts were carried out for the execution of the pilots. The

				iterations were increased at least by 3
2	Cost for new product development	Manufacturer	10-20% reduction	Manufacturers have eliminated the costs of market analysis and reduced those costs of design and prototyping thanks to the collaboration with the Fablabs.
2.1	Market Analysis cost	Manufacturer	100% reduction (free)	The use of the market analysis tool is completely free
2.2	Design cost	Manufacturer	5-10% reduction	Just changing traditional process to computer 3D Design, time reduction is obtained. This parameter was compared by manufacturers with the traditional processes to estimate cost reduction.
2.3	Prototype time cost	Manufacturer	50% reduction	3D printing is able to obtain prototypes in 2 or 3 days (just depending on part size), while traditional processes need at least 1 or 2 weeks.
2.4	Prototype precision	Manufacturer	From dm to mm	Sculptures made by hand are much rougher than the ones developed using 3D printing technologies
2.5	Operation margin	Manufacturer	10-20% increase	For Manufacturers, this process is outsourced. The time cost reduction affected the operation margin in proportion
3	Quality of the entire process	Manufacturer, FabLabs,	5-10% quality improvement	Taking into consideration

		Experts, End-Users		prototype precision and decreasing errors and iterations on certification, the overall quality of the process increased in proportion depending on the number of iterations and errors.
3.1	Number of issues	Manufacturer Fablabs	20-30% reduction	Involving Safety experts on design stage, manufacturers and Fablabs understand from the beginning all problems that the final product might have. This issue allows manufacturers to prevent easily solvable errors in the design. On the production stage, in order to obtain certification, manufacturers only need one or two iterations
3.2	Average rating of the ToyLabs Platform	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts, End-Users	3-4/5	The different stakeholders of the platform have evaluated the platform with an average score of 7 out of 10, which translates into 3.5 out of 5.
3.3	FabLabs Quality of Service	FabLabs	3-4/5	The different stakeholders of the platform have evaluated the platform with an average score of 7 out of 10, which translates into 3.5 out of 5.
3.4	Experts Quality of Service	Experts	3-4/5	The different stakeholders of the platform have

				evaluated the platform with an average score of 7 out of 10, which translates into 3.5 out of 5.
4	Safety Levels	Manufacturer	All of them (is this possible?) If it is not then at least 90% of them	To date, AIJU has been the only organization accredited as Safety Expert. AIJU has assessed safety issues in a total of four projects. As we incorporate more Safety Experts, the number of safety evaluations will increase.
5	Level of participation of stakeholders (apart from the manufacturer)	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts, End-Users	3-6	As previously verified, all the stakeholders considered for the ToyLabs Methodology and Platform have participated in the main pilots and many of the secondary scenarios.
5.1	Number of ideas	End Users	5-10	67 products, 63 designs, 35 prototypes
5.2	Number of comments on toys	Manufacturer	>30	63 negotiation messages exchanged,
5.3	Number of stakeholders answering a request	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts	5-10 (depending on the request)	17 feedback messages exchanged
5.4	Number of new collaborations	FabLab, Experts	20-30% increase (relative to current collaborations)	53 collaborations in total in the platform.
5.5	Number of services by partner	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts	2-5 (depending on the partner)	39 AR models

Table 10 - KPIs consecution

4. BUCHAREST TSIG WORKSHOP

4.1. INTRODUCTION OF THE TSIG WORKSHOP

The pilots have been carried out from M10 to M18, within the tasks of the WP5. During this work package, different processes of creation of new products have been executed through the ToyLabs methodology and platform. As already specified in previous points of this deliverable, the scenarios carried out, reached different levels of development: two of them have reached the prototyping stage.

Throughout this process, the following stakeholders have been involved: FabLabs, Toy Manufacturers, Safety Experts and Childhood Experts. All of them have participated, contributing with their expertise, in the development phases of new toys in which their collaboration has been necessary.

In the last phase of the pilots, the TSIG Workshop has been executed, through which 9 of the more than 100 childhood experts who collaborate in the processes of creating new toys through the ToyLabs platform have met. The main task of the childhood experts during the pilots has been to provide feedback to the different designs and prototypes developed as well as suggest any suggestions they consider necessary to the improvement of the platform. In short, this TSIG aimed to collect all information possible that childhood experts can provide to the project partners, in order to improve the functionalities of the platform.

4.2. INTRODUCTION OF THE ATENDEES

The following table introduces the nine attendees of the TSIG Workshop. A short description of their expertise and the company and nationality details are also described:

Name and Surname	Expertise	Curriculum	Nationality
Úrsula Perona	Psychologist expert in children	Úrsula M ^a Perona Mira is a Child and Adolescent Psychologist. She has a degree in Psychology with a specialization in methodology and didactics for e-learning. In addition, she has a master's degree in Child and Adolescent Clinical Psychology. Her work focuses on evaluation, diagnosis and psychological	Spain

		intervention with adults, adolescents and children. It also elaborates didactic materials and gives courses and talks for town councils, schools and associations.	
Lucia Perez	Psychologist expert in disabilities	<p>Graduated in Communication Sciences at the "University of Perugia" in Italy and specialized with two Masters courses, one in "Event Organization" at the "Parco della Musica" in Rome and one in "Coordination of Childhood Services" at the "Roma Tre" University.</p> <p>From 2013 she is the promoter of the Education Section in the Festival "Conversations on the future" in Lecce. She is also the CEO and Co-Founder of Boboto, B-CORP that promotes activities oriented to the world of education, inclusivity and social innovation, which aims to have a positive impact on society and the biosphere. She is the person of reference for Puglia of Fondazione Montessori Italia and co-founder of the "Coderdojo Lecce" group, active since 2013.</p>	Spain
Altin Lubonja	Toys and Books Publisher and Distributor	<p>Altin Lubonja has studied Physics and Mathematics. His expertise is teaching math and physics to students of high schools and universities. He teaches strategy games and puzzle solving on student clubs of high schools in Thessaloniki (Greece).</p> <p>Moreover, he is the director and owner of Mathimatiki Vivliothiki, publisher of educative science books, games and distributor of strategy and card games, mind toys, puzzles, constructions and educative games and many others.</p>	Greece
Iliana Morelli	Montessori and coding educator	Iliana Morelli holds a degree in Educational theory and practice.	Italy

		<p>She also holds two master degrees in science of communication and educational coordination.</p> <p>She is the founder and administrator of Boboto, Benefit Company founded with the aim of promoting activities oriented to the world of education, inclusiveness and social innovation through collaboration with public and private bodies, with research institutions and with the civil society. Iliana is the creator of the MONTESSORI 3D project, Boboto's flagship project, created to make Montessori pedagogy as usable and inclusive, in all educational contexts, in the school and outside the school, with teachers and with the family nucleus.</p>	
Istvan Csucsak	Toys Publisher and Distributor	<p>Managing, tracking and increasing sales, research and localization of new products. Direct brand management, product launches, advertising, sales collateral and tradeshow marketing. His main activities are:</p> <p>Continuous survey of the market and expanding our offers.</p> <p>Management of web sales campaigns</p> <p>Executing the logistics of acquisition of new products</p>	Romania
Nagy Gábor	Toys Publisher and Distributor	<p>Managing, tracking and increasing sales, research and localization of new products. Direct brand management, product launches, advertising, sales collateral and tradeshow marketing. His main activities are:</p> <p>Developing, localizing and launching new toys and board games for the Romanian market.</p> <p>Cooperation with the Romanian Mind Fitness Games board game publishing company in developing</p>	Romania

		<p>new games, gameplay testing and thematic research.</p> <p>Within MATRISZ Association, organization of national board game playing events.</p> <p>Cooperation with board game clubs and management of board game competitions.</p> <p>Representation of our products at national and international fairs and conventions.</p>	
Rebecca Hellwing	Child Psychologist and Family Psychotherapist	Rebecca Hellwing holds a B.A. in Sociology. Her professional background is working as community projects and safety audit coordinator, executive co-producer, workshop director, PR consultant and at the present she works as an account executive.	Germany
Teodora Maravela	Psychologist expert in children and disabilities - School	<p>Teodora Maravela holds a degree on Psychology and her occupational skill is Psychology and science of education. She also holds a Mastering Specialist in educational counselling and intervention in school and vocation.</p> <p>Regarding her professional experience, she is working at Braila School of Inclusive Education and at SC Psihoforworld SRL. She works with children with special education needs, with a view to their recovery and school integration. Counseling and psycho-pedagogical intervention.</p>	Romania
Anca David	Psychologist expert in children and disabilities - School	Anca David holds a degree in Psychology at the University of West Timisoara with an specialization of socio-psycho-pedagogy. Currently, she is a Professor of psycho-pedagogue in Braila School of Inclusive Education. Her main responsibilities are psychological counselling, psychotherapy and speech therapy. Moreover, she has experience in coordinating	Romania

		European projects; and is the Manager of SC Psihoforworld SRL.	
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Table 11 - TSIG Experts Attendance

4.3. DESCRIPTION OF THE WORKSHOP

In this section the course of the workshop is described. First, the agenda is described to subsequently reflect the activities carried out during the day.

4.3.1. AGENDA

The agenda was developed with the objective of holding the Workshop on the morning of May 29, from 9 am to 2 pm.

The Workshop was divided into three main parts:

- 1) The first part, from 9 a.m. to 10.30 a.m., focused on the presentation of both the project partners and the invited experts. There was also a brief reminder of the objective of the ToyLabs project. Regarding Singular Logic, the new functionalities of the ToyLabs platform were introduced to the experts; moreover, doubts about the operation of the platform were solved.
- 2) In the second part of the workshop, from 10.45 am to 12.45 pm, the experts were able to see first-hand the new functionalities of the platform. Part of that time was spent on providing new feedback and checking the correct functioning of the platform's new features.
- 3) Finally, in the third part of the workshop, from 1:30 pm to 2:00 pm, the children's experts discussed the usability, the bugs found, the usefulness, and the interest that the platform arouses, to conclude the session with the completion of a survey.

Following is the agenda of the TSIG Workshop of May 29:

Time	Issue	Responsible
09.00-09.15	Welcome Partners & Experts	AIJU
09.15-09.45	Partners and TSIG presentation	AIJU
09.45-10.00	Session Plan	AIJU
10.00-10.30	New Features Platform Training	SINGULAR LOGIC
10.30-10.45	Coffee Break	
10.45-12.45	Workshop ToyLabs – AR tool usage and feedback process.	SINGULAR LOGIC
12.45-13.30	Coffee Break	
13.30-13.45	Platform and AR tool feedback gathering	AIJU

13.45-14.00	Next tasks and homework for June	AIJU
14.00	End of Meeting	AIJU

Table 12 - Agenda of the TSIG

4.3.2 ACTIVITIES OF THE WORKSHOP

- The first part of the workshop was the welcoming to all attendees by Mr. Raúl Esteban.

- Secondly, a brief description of the project objective and ToyLabs Methodology was done by Ms Carolina Santonja. This was done in order to ensure that childhood experts are aware of the purpose of their attendance.

- Thirdly, Mr. Raúl Esteban explained to the experts the different tasks that would be done during the workshop. The agenda was introduced at this point.

- Mr. Marios Phinikettos, then, introduced the new features of the ToyLabs Platform, and the way that the AR Engine is used, to the experts. Moreover, a small discussion regarding questions in the way of use of the platform was carried out by the attendees. For this reason, he made use of his laptop and smartphone, with which he reviewed each of the modules of the platform, explaining the novelties introduced in recent months and resolving the doubts raised by the experts. Then, with the smartphone, he showed and explained the operation of the Augmented Reality app, with which experts can visualize a physical environment of the real world, through a technological device (in this case the smartphone). This device adds virtual information to existing physical information; in this case, the virtual prototypes of new toys. This way; the tangible physical elements are combined with virtual elements, thus creating an augmented reality in real time, which helps the childhood experts to evaluate the prototypes. The AR prototype Boing 747 was used as an example for this presentation.

- A coffee break followed the new features training session. The coffee break helped the attendees to enjoy a more relaxed workshop. The experts shared professional experiences among themselves and with the members of the ToyLabs project.

Image 39 - TSIG Workshop session

- One of the most important tasks followed the coffee break. The experts had two hours for testing the new features of the platform, detect bugs, ask any other questions to the ToyLabs partners, provide new feedback to the different toy creation projects in the platform, etc. To ensure this task was adequately met, the project partners gave the experts a total of 6 iPads, with which they logged into the platform and carried out the proposed tasks.

- Afterwards, a discussion about the main aspects of the platform, its usability, its added value, etc. was carried out, with the objective of making a reflection that helps the subsequent completion of the questionnaire, which was the last task of the workshop. It took about 30 minutes to fill the survey.

4.4. CHILDHOOD EXPERTS' EVALUATION

4.4.1. EVALUATION TYPOLOGY

Online surveys were chosen to carry out the evaluation of the platform and the workshop by the experts. This has been considered the best option for the following reasons:

- 1) Simplicity in the elaboration of the questionnaires.
- 2) Simplicity in its completion.
- 3) Instant information collection.
- 4) Quantitative analysis of the results automatically.

The questionnaire was structured in 6 themes:

- 1) Usability: In this subject, aspects such as ease of use of the platform, intuitiveness, speed of response, among others related to usability were evaluated.
- 2) Bugs: In this topic, the objective was to collect all the operating errors detected by the experts in childhood. This improved the performance through the solution of those bugs.
- 3) Usefulness: information has been obtained on the usefulness of the platform to solve the problems detected among the SMEs of the European toy sector.
- 4) Interest: The interest raised by the platform in the specific target of childhood experts is collected through this section in the questionnaire.
- 5) Exploitation: In this section, experts were asked for information on how they consider that the platform should be economically exploited.
- 6) Conclusions: Finally, questions about the platform's strengths and weaknesses, about satisfaction with the day, etc.

4.4.2. SAMPLE AND NUMBER OF FILLED EVALUATION SHEETS

Out of all the childhood experts who use the platform (>100), nine people were selected to attend the TSIG Workshop. These people were selected for their suitability, while also trying to represent the heterogeneity of the specializations of all childhood experts.

From these nine people, eight of them have answered the survey.

4.4.3. RESULTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No [732559].

The results have been analysed, at first, individually, question by question. For each of the questions, the answers have been expressed in the form of a graph or table and then the results have been analysed qualitatively. In a second phase, the information obtained was structured in a table in which the main strengths, suggestions and conclusions of each of the analysed aspects are summarized.

Following that, the results of the sheet are detailed, following the 6 different themes in which it was structured:

Usability of the Platform

Usability refers to the ease or difficulty of interacting with the platform and each of its different modules/pages...

This part of the survey was formed by 6 specific questions.

Following are the results of this evaluation:

For question 1: “How easy or difficult did you find the overall interaction with the platform?”

8 responses

To this question, six of eight people answered that they found it easy to interact with the platform. One person found it very easy and the last one neither easy nor difficult.

For question 2: “How easy or difficult did you find the 'Sign Up' and 'Log In' processes of the platform?”

8 responses

It was agreed at the international meetings that the sign up for the platform should offer many options (through Google and Facebook accounts and also using the e-mail address) in order to simplify the access to the platform.

The answers to this questions reflected that this objective was achieved. Everyone answered “very easy” or “easy” to this question, with the pre-eminence of the first option.

For question 3: “When logged into the Platform, how easy or difficult was your interaction with the platform, or put simply, how easy or difficult was it to understand the overall layout and the different buttons and sections?”

8 responses

The answers to this question reflect, following the previous ones, the ease of use of the platform, since 87,5% of the experts answered that they found it “very easy” or “easy” to understand the overall layout and the buttons distribution.

For question 4: Having 1 to mean “slow” and 10 “fast”, how responsive do you consider the platform to be?

The answers for this question concentrated on the values 7, 8 and 9. This means that the response of the platform is considered fast by the majority of the experts.

For question 5: What do you think of the interaction with the different sections of the platform?

This was one of the most important questions of the usability section. Here, the ease or difficulty of use of the platform is segregated by the different modules of it.

Overall, the responses to all the sections are satisfactory, but some differences can be found:

- The Messaging section was the one that the experts found easier to use. Almost all answers were “very easy”.
- The Prototype Section (AR Engine) was the one most difficult to use according to experts' experiences, with the higher rate of answers giving the answer “neither easy nor difficult”.
- Designs section and Provide Feedback were found “easy” to use by most of the experts. The second most chosen option was “very easy” for both sections.

For question 6: Do you have any other considerations/suggestions about the usability of the ToyLabs Platform?

This was an open question. Seven out of nine interviewees wrote down suggestions. Following the answers for the question are reflected:

Nº Interviewee	Consideration/suggestion
1	It will be interesting that the details of the products are well specified, because if we don't have the minimum information, we cannot evaluate the prototypes correctly.
2	It is necessary to insert a precise product sheet with all the details of the prototype.
3	A UX test should be recommended because some functions cannot be found naturally.
4	Language/localization: Small German companies have limited language (English) skills. This country leads non-English speaking countries. Add a box for online print/media/influencers Forum (think Trip Advisor) Content - experts write articles or listicles.
5	The manufacturer should make a detailed description of the toy. Depending on the age, consider the material from which the toy was made.
6	I think you should add the option to add videos with the way the product works
7	- In general I think it would be very important to include an initial button providing the following information: 1) What's the aim of the platform and the sort of users for whom it has been developed; 2) how the platform works. - Products design section: it would be advisable to include a complete description of the product (size, material...) explanations from the designer (why it's an innovation)

Table 13 - Childhood experts suggestions about the usability of the Platform

This information can be summarized in the following suggestions:

- ✓ Ensure that designs and prototypes count with more variables for achieving a detailed information section about the product.
 - Add an option for uploading videos explaining the functioning of the developments.
 - Boxes for description of size, material, innovative facts, etc.
- ✓ Add a usability test for the first use of the platform, in order to familiarize users.
 - An initial button providing information about the aim of the platform and the sorting of users for whom it has been developed.
- ✓ Add other languages more than English.

Bugs

One of the purposes of the workshop was to identify and reflect any kind of errors in the platform functioning. For this reason, the survey included one question with two different parts related to this:

Question 1: Did you experience any error in the Platform operation?

For this question, 4 people said that they experienced errors and 3 people did not find any errors.

Following, the bugs detected are listed:

Nº Interviewee	Bugs detected
1	Disconnection.
1	The link of my website didn't work.
2	Editing the organisation data error 401 and
2	When joining an organisation, I cannot see the shared product, i.e. what is shared with the company.
3	misspelled words
4	401

Table 14 - Bugs detected by the Childhood Experts

Usefulness of the ToyLabs Platform

At this section the objective was to collect information regarding how useful the experts found the platform and its different sections. For this, 3 different questions were raised:

Question 1: Having 1 as "useless" and 10 as "really useful", how useful do you think the different sections of ToyLabs Platform are for the objective of increasing the added value and the quality of the process of creating new toys?

At this question, our aim was to obtain information about each of the 5 main modules of the platform (the ones which Childhood Experts are related with). For this reason, one closed categorized question, with more than one variable was raised to the interviewees.

The results obtained were the following:

- For “Dashboard” section: five over eight people consider that this section is really useful, with more than 8 points over 10 in the Likert scale. Two people rated one and two and one did not answer this question.
- For “Design” section: the same results were obtained as with "Dashboard". Five over eight people consider that this section is really useful, with more than 8 points over 10 in the Likert scale. Two people rated one and two and one did not answer this question.
- For “Prototype” section (AR Engine): for this section we obtained similar results. Two people rated with one and two while over five people rated with, at least, eight in the Likert scale.
- For “Messaging” section: here, the results obtained are the same as in “Dashboard” and “Design” section; with five interviewees who rated the section with eight or more in the Likert scale.
- For “providing feedback”: This is the section in which the answers were more segregated. While two people evaluated with a 2, three did with a 10, one interviewee evaluated with a 7 in the Likert scale.

With these results we can see that there is a divergence in the opinions of the experts in childhood regarding the usefulness of the different sections of the ToyLabs Platform. Even so, there is a majority of interviewees who consider all sections useful or very useful for the objectives set out in the ToyLabs project.

Question 2: Having 1 as "useless" and 10 as "really useful", how useful do you find the ToyLabs Platform in general for the objective of increasing the added value and quality of the process of creating new toys?

The conclusions that we have reached previously are confirmed with the answers to these questions, in which all the interviewees have assessed with more than five on the Likert scale the general usefulness of the ToyLabs platform for the objectives identified in the project.

Question 3: If you have any further suggestions or considerations regarding the Platform usefulness write them down here, like its aspects that can be improved, other points of view, features, etc.

Two people have answered this question. The suggestions were as follows:

Nº Interviewee	Suggestion/consideration
1	Create a section for young people who want to get involved in creating toys (young people studying art and future IT). In this way, entrepreneurship among young people will be encouraged in line with EU objectives
2	I think this application should also be presented in schools so that young people can create toys because they have a different perspective on toys, and the age difference between youngsters and children who use toys is lower and it is easier for young people to figure out what kids who will use toys prefer. Once this application is presented to young people, they will also present it to parents who can also have innovative ideas for future toys

Table 15 - Childhood Experts Suggestions regarding Platform usefulness

Interest in the ToyLabs Platform

At this section we aimed to know whether experts would be interested in still using the platform after the end of the pilot scenarios. Moreover, we aimed to know whether they would suggest the use of this platform to colleagues. Six questions were developed in order to collect information related to this topic. Following that, the summarized results of this section can be found:

Question 1: Do you think the ToyLabs Platform is interesting?

- ✓ In this question, six people out of seven considered the platform “really interesting”, the remaining expert considered it as "quite interesting".

Questions 2 and 3: What do you find most interesting about the Platform? And, what do you think can be improved in the Platform?

This was an open question and the answers were as follows:

Nº Interviewee	Most interesting	What can be improved
1	The possibility for the toy manufacturer to interacting and revive important information about their prototypes for different experts.	More information for the prototypes
2	The possibility of interaction	The description of the idea of the game, we need more details
3	The shorter time for the development process	User interface
4	Provides a platform for collaborations specifically for SME's and the toy industry.	
5	Facilities offered	
6	I like it and it's a beautiful idea	

Table 16 - Childhood Experts suggestions regarding most interesting vs thing to be improved.

Question 4: Would you consider using the platform in the future?

7 responses

Six out of seven people consider using the platform in the future, while one expert does not know.

Question 5: Having 1 as "not recommended at all" and 10 as "strongly recommended", what is the probability that you recommend the use of the platform to your colleagues?

All experts will recommend the use of this platform to colleagues, in some extent. All of them rated with 6 or more in the Likert scale.

Question 6: If you have anything else to add regarding your interest in the Platform, please explain it here:

Following are the considerations that interviewees wanted to provide regarding the interest that the platform provoke.

Nº Interviewee	Description of the interest of the Platform
1	It should be developed better under different aspects
2	I think it is a great idea to host "training workshops" to introduce the platform to potential members.

Table 17 - Childhood Experts suggestions regarding interest of the Platform

ToyLabs Platform Exploitation

In this part of the document, one of the most important parts of the questionnaire is analysed. The collaboration of the childhood experts in order to define a realistic exploitation plan with application capacity is necessary. The experts have contributed their suggestions regarding their willingness to pay, about whether they would like to get benefits for their services and how they would like to be paid.

Six questions were proposed for this section. The first 4 questions are focused in knowing if experts consider that they should pay an amount of money and also the way of implementation of the payments.

The fifth question aims to know whether experts consider that they should get paid for their services or not. The last question asks experts if they consider another option for making the Platform economically self-sufficient.

Question 1 to 4: These are the questions raised regarding the payment by the childhood experts for the use of the platform:

- 1) Answer from 1 to 10, with 1 "definitely not" and 10 "definitely yes", if you would pay a monthly subscription fee for the use of the platform.
- 2) Answer from 1 to 10, with 1 "definitely not" and 10 "definitely yes", if you would pay a fixed amount of money for each use (project enrolled) of the platform.
- 3) Answer from 1 to 10, with 1 "definitely not" and 10 "definitely yes", if you would pay to promote yourself as an expert (placing you among the first in the list of options).
- 4) Answer from 1 to 10, with 1 "definitely not" and 10 "definitely yes", if you would consider paying anything for using the Platform.

For this questions, the following results were obtained:

- ✓ For the first question, most of the interviewees would not consider paying a monthly subscription fee for the use of the platform. Only two over the seven responses were affirmative.
- ✓ For the second question, opinions are divided. While three experts would not pay a fixed amount of money for each use, four experts would be willing to pay for each use (project enrolled) of the platform.
- ✓ The third question was related with paying to promote yourself as experts. For this option, most experts would not be willing to pay. Only two consider this way of payment as a good option.
- ✓ Finally, the results concerning the question which englobes all ways of payments, and that ask experts if they would consider paying anything in any way for the use of the Platform are shown in the figure below:

Answer from 1 to 10, with 1 "definitely not" and 10 "definitely yes", if you would consider paying anything for using the Platform.

7 responses

As it can be seen, there is a big segregation in the opinion of the experts regarding paying. Three of them do not agree with paying for the use of the platform while four of them strongly agree with payments.

Question 5: How do you consider you should get paid for the services you provide?

7 responses

This question aims to know how childhood experts consider they should get paid for offering their services in the platform. The option most selected was “by each service provided”, while “a monthly fixed amount” and “a percentage of the benefit” were chosen by one expert each. No one considered another option for getting paid.

Final considerations

In this last section, we wanted experts to reflect their general impressions of the Platform, as well as the TSIG Workshop. For this objective, seven questions have been developed.

Question 1: Having 1 as “Nothing” and 10 as “A lot”, tell us how much did you enjoy the Workshop today.

7 responses

As reflected in the answers to the question, practically all of the attendees were very satisfied with the TSIG. The evaluations were between nine and ten, according to the Likert scale, in 7 of the 8 responses. Only one interviewee rated the day with a five.

Question 2: Do you consider this Platform will be adopted in the toy market sector?

7 responses

Experts agreed that the market sector will adopt, at least to some extent, the use of the platform.

Question 3: Do you consider that the use of this platform will increase the performance of the toys created through it in the market?

Here, it is important to pay attention to the percentage of respondents who have selected the "not really" option to the question. 28.6% of respondents have opted for this option. These results will be taken into account to improve the platform with the suggestions provided in this questionnaire.

Question 4: From 1 to 5, do you consider that the toys developed following ToyLabs Method and Platform will compete with big toy brands more effectively?

Two experts out of seven considered that this platform will not really help SME's to compete with big toy brands, while, four people think that it will and one is in the middle of the Likert scale.

This means that not all of them agree with the usefulness of the platform for helping SME's, but, still, more people consider that it is useful.

Question 5: This question consists in two main parts:

- Would you buy a toy you have helped create?
- Would you recommend a toy you have helped create?

For both questions, the seven answers were yes.

Question 6: What do you consider is the main strength of the ToyLabs Platform?

Nº Interviewee	Main strength of the ToyLabs Platform
1	The possibility for little manufacturers to do better toys with the opinion of several experts.
2	If developed better and with more ideas could become a point of reference.
3	The possibility to implement a product on a distant market.
4	It makes it easier for collaborations and easier to identify new partners and toys that can complement each other.
5	Collaboration of specialists
6	That you can express your free creativity by creating a toy

Table 18 - Childhood Experts Main Strengths of the platform suggestions

Question 7: What do you consider to be the main weakness of the ToyLabs Platform?

Nº Interviewee	Main weaknesses of the Toylabs Platform
1	It is still too basic

2	The lack of users
3	<p>Final Comments:</p> <p>Pay to Promote oneself as an expert: I do not like that idea because it is not authentic and gives the small and mighty business/individual limited opportunities to be seen. However, instead you might offer sponsored content but not pay to promote as vendor.</p> <p>Pay anything for using the platform: One idea is to sell advertising space to trade fairs (conferences) but let the small businesses collaborate.</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>You have great platforms for engagement but it needs to be developed and used. For example, don't underestimate TWITTER!! However, it takes time and one shouldn't drop and go. There are multiple Toylab profiles on Twitter but how do you stand out? Is there a #hashtag that you use specifically or perhaps your members? What about a Twitter Party to launch?</p>

Table 19 - Childhood Experts Main Weaknesses of the platform suggestions

4.4.4. TOYLABS PLATFORM FEELINGS OF EXPERTS

After each question of the questionnaire has been analysed, we carried out a final reflection, in which the aspects detected by the most relevant childhood experts are compiled for the conclusion of both the pilots and the project.

To do this, a table has been drawn up in which the most relevant aspects of the assessments of the childhood experts are reflected in each of the topics covered in the questionnaire. These assessments are organized into: 1 platform strengths, 2 aspects susceptible to improvement and 3 final considerations.

	Strengths	Improvements and aspects to take into account	Final Considerations
Usability of the ToyLabs Platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experts consider the platform easy to use. • Experts consider it very easy to Sing Up and Log In to the platform. • Experts consider the platform is fast when interacting with it. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prototype Section (AR Engine) is considered as the most difficult tool to use. • People need more detail in the design description and prototype. • Add a section in designs and prototypes descriptions in which it could be possible to upload a video-description of the product. • The Platform is only available in English. Need of adding more European languages. 	<p>Despite the fact that the ToyLabs Platform has been considered to be easy to use by the childhood experts, some of the features and functionalities of the platform are hard to find. They propose to solve this with a video-tutorial.</p> <p>Sing Up and Log in have been considered as the most “user-friendly” section of the Platform.</p>
Bugs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The bugs found are not critical for the proper functioning of the ToyLabs Platform. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main bugs found are: disconnection of the platform, links to external webs did not work, error 401 when editing the organization data, problems when join to an organization (products are not shown), misspelled words. 	<p>At the date of the Workshop, certain errors still existed. Despite this, it was possible to carry out the workshop effectively. The errors were corrected the week after the Workshop.</p>

<p>Usefulness of the ToyLabs Platform</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All the childhood experts considered the ToyLabs Platform useful for the objective of increasing the added value and quality of the process of creating new toys. Most of the experts evaluated positively the usefulness of the five sections analysed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider adding a new section for young people who want to get involved in creating toys. Prototype section (AR Engine) is considered as the “less useful”. Important to keep this in mind for new updates. 	<p>In general, experts evaluated the usefulness of the platform positively. On the other hand, there are aspects that can be improved.</p>
<p>Interest in the ToyLabs Platform</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Everyone rated positively the interest that the Platform arouses. The speedup of the development process has been one of the most recurrent benefits detected by experts with the use of the Platform. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The experts agreed that, with small changes in the interface of the platform, it would be much more attractive to the end user. This would improve the interaction and, therefore, the interest in its use. 	<p>All experts have a good opinion about the Platform. All of them considered it interesting. The possibility for the toy manufacturers to interact and collect important information before production is the most appreciated features.</p>
<p>Exploitation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conclusive results were obtained determining the way with which childhood experts would obtain benefits through the use of the platform. The form chosen by the majority of experts is "by service provided". 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experts did not agree to paying for the use of the platform. Three of them do not agree with paying for the use of the platform while four of them strongly agree with payments. 	<p>It is certain that childhood experts will not pay any type of fee for using the platform. On the other hand, they will receive compensation for the assistance provided in the different designs of new products that are carried out on the platform. All this is detailed in deliverable 7.5</p>

Table 20 - Complied suggestions of Childhood Experts

5. WALKTHROUGH FOR THE UTILISATION OF THE TOYLABS PLATFORM

5.1. GUESTS

Guests that visit the ToyLabs platform, can browse public Products, Designs and Prototypes, as published by the users and, view a list of all the professionals in the platform (organisations and freelancers) as well as visit their profiles. To interact with anything (i.e. like a public product or leave a comment), someone should create an account.

5.2. LOGIN - REGISTRATION - PROFILE CREATION

A new user can register using his name, email address and password or use his Facebook or Google account to login (in which case, the first time an account is created automatically). After the registration, the user is redirected to the dashboard, and is prompted to edit his personal profile. This step is mandatory for users that plan to use the platform for more than liking and leaving comments on products.

The screenshot shows the registration interface for the ToyLabs platform. At the top center is the ToyLabs logo, which features a stylized 'T' and 'L' with a gear and a lightbulb. Below the logo is a registration form with the following elements:

- A text input field for 'Name' with a person icon on the left.
- A text input field for 'Email' with an envelope icon on the left.
- Two text input fields for 'Password' and 'Confirm Password', each with a lock icon on the left.
- A checkbox labeled 'I agree to the Terms and Conditions'.
- A link: 'Already have an account? Go to the [Login](#) page.'
- An orange 'Register' button.

Image 40 - Register Screenshot

When a user creates his personal profile (not available when editing), he can set his role in the platform (Toy Manufacturer, Fablab, Safety Expert, Security Expert, Retailer or, just End User). After creating his personal profile, and if the selected role is not End User, he is prompted to join or create an organisation. An organisation (for the platform) can be a company, a group of people that work together (not a legal entity), or even, just the user. In that case, organisation type should be set to Freelancer, and the organisation will act as the user's professional profile.

5.3. DASHBOARD - MY PRODUCTS

Each user that has his profile(s) set, has full access to the ToyLabs platform. In the dashboard page, he can:

- Create a new product
- View the state of all his products
- View his active collaborations
- View his archived collaborations
- See his messages
- See his notifications

5.4. CREATING A NEW PRODUCT - CONCEPT PHASE

Using the appropriate button in the dashboard, the user will be presented with a form for creating a new product. In this form, the user will be asked to fill in a title, a description of the product (as he conceptualises it), select a toy category and the suitable ages. Then he is prompted to fill information concerning the person to whom the IP belongs to (the user himself, or his organisation) and if he wants the product to be made public and visible to the homepage. Finally, the user can upload images (schematics, drawings, concept art or even photographs) and files (budgeting, research material, etc.) for the product. Keep in mind that anything uploaded under the “Files” section is only visible by the product owner (and, if the product is owned by an organisation, the members of that organisation). The images are visible by anyone that has access to the product: everyone in case of a public product, or anyone asked to collaborate on a design/prototype of the product, even before they sign any NDA agreement. So be careful not to upload any confidential images.

The screenshot shows the 'New Product' creation form. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Dashboard', 'Members', and 'About' tabs, and a user profile 'Raúl Esteban'. The form title is 'New Product' with a 'Back to Dashboard' button. The form is divided into several sections: 'General' with 'Title' and 'Description' fields; 'Category' with a dropdown menu; 'Suitable for Ages From' and 'To' with dropdown menus and a note: 'Tentative ages. You can change the age group later, if needed.'; 'Legal' with radio buttons for 'Myself' (selected) and 'My Organization', and a checkbox for 'Do you want to make your product public (can be seen by everyone)?' with 'No' selected; and 'Images' with a note: 'For informational images only. If your product is public, these are made public as well.'

Image 41 - New Product creation Screenshot

After a product is created, the user is redirected to the dashboard again, where its progress is clearly visible. At first, only the **Concept** phase is enabled. The product owner can edit the product (using the small blue button to the right),

and pressing **Continue to Market Analysis** (bottom left) to unlock **Research** and **Design** phases.

5.5. RESEARCH - MARKET ANALYSIS PHASE

After creating the concept, the user will have at his disposal the tool "Social Analytics & Market Trend Analysis". This tool allows you to carry out an effective and simple study on the trends in the market. The tool makes use of keywords, which are entered by the user, as well as parameters and concepts to perform a more detailed analysis. Among the different advanced options are time settings, the possibility of selecting social networks on which to do the study and the possibility of selecting "only influencers".

Image 42 - Market Trend Analysis screenshot

The results obtained are shown in the form of most mentioned tags and graphics with trends.

5.6. DESIGN PHASE

At any time during the product creation lifecycle, after the Design Phase is unlocked, the product owner (or anyone in his organisation), can create any number of product designs. Creating a design is straight forward, and nothing to describe in detail. Note that in Designs (as with prototypes later) the "Files" section is shared with collaborators, when one is added to the design.

After a design is created, the user has 7 available options:

Image 43 - Product Designs options screenshots

5.6.1. EDIT DESIGN

This option is self-explanatory.

5.6.2. AR MODELS - AUGMENT REALITY MODULE

This is a link to a page concerning the Augmented Reality models. At this page the user can see a list of AR models (along with the numbers of downloads, comments and the user average rating) and options to create new ones and edit or delete existing ones. In addition to that, the user has access to an analysis of user interaction for each AR model (clicking on its name), where the product owner can view what users believe about the AR model.

Creating an AR model, requires (in addition to the AR model files) a title and a description as well as defining 3 feedback categories for the users. These categories default to Design, Features and Novelty, while a 5-star rating system is employed.

5.6.3. CREATE NEW VERSION

Archives (see below) the current version of the design, and redirects the user to a pre-filled (title, description) design creation form to create a new version of a design. Every collaboration that was formed in the current version of the design is archived, and the new version is clear of collaborations (must use the partner matching module to search for partners again).

5.6.4. FEEDBACK

Opens a page with all the partners the user has active collaborations (on current design) with. Clicking on an organisation, the feedback discussion thread between the product owner and the collaborator can be accessed.

5.6.5. COLLABORATIONS - PARTNER MATCHING MODULE

Here the user can see an Overview of his collaborations along with their status (negotiating, accepted, archived). Clicking on an organisation name, the negotiation thread is accessed, and (if the collaboration is in negotiation phase) messages can be exchanged. Keep in mind that messages both in feedback and collaborations pages can be accessed through the messages menu (at the top navigation bar, clicking on the envelop icon).

The screenshot shows the 'Collaborations' page for the design 'SmartDolls'. It features a navigation bar with 'Dashboard', 'Members', and 'About'. A user profile for 'OLGA TRAVINA' is visible in the top right. The main content area has tabs for 'Overview' and 'Search'. Below the tabs is a search bar with the placeholder 'Search by name...'. Underneath is an 'ADVANCED SEARCH' section with several filter categories: 'I am looking for a:' (Toy Manufacturer, FabLab, Child Expert, Safety Expert, Retailer), 'That has any the following competencies:' (3D Modelling, CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation, Inkjet Printing, Mould Casting, Soldering Station, 3D Printing, Circuit Production, Knitting Machine, Plastic Transformation, Vacuum Forming, 3D Scanning, CNC Milling, Laser Cutting, Sewing Machine, Vinyl Cutting), 'Scale of production needed:' (Prototyping Only, Small, Medium, Large, Extra Large), 'I will pay using:' (Bank Transfer, Credit Card, Paypal, Check, Bitcoin), and 'Payment will be:' (On Delivery, In 15 Days, In 30 Days, In 45 Days, In 60 Days, In 90 Days). There are 'Clear' and 'Search' buttons at the bottom of the search form.

In addition to the list of organisations the user is collaborating with, he can search for more organisations to collaborate with. This is done through the search interface in two ways:

- Quick search: typing the name of the organisation in the search field and clicking on the organisation's name
- Advanced search: filling his requirements, and in the list of organisations presented, press the contact button

In the advanced search, the results are ranked and sorted based on user requirements. Clicking the contact button, the product owner can message the desired organization's owner about a collaboration on a design, exchange files (NDA agreements, contracts, schematics etc.) and finally add him as a collaborator to the design.

Note here that while every member of an organisation can contact other organisations to collaborate on a design, **only** the organisation owner can add someone as a collaborator.

5.6.6. CREATE PROTOTYPE

Clicking on the create prototype option, the design is archived and the prototype creation form is presented, pre-filled with the design's title and description. Creating a prototype, enables the **Prototype Phase**.

5.6.7. ARCHIVE DESIGN

Archiving triggers two actions:

- puts a design in a special status, where the user can only access the AR models and the feedback options
- for each collaboration, asks both partners to rate the collaboration between them based on Quality, Co-operation and Communication.

The feedback interface is found in the same page as messages and notifications.

5.7 PROTOTYPE PHASE

Prototype Phase is very similar to the Design phase. In this page, the user can generate as many prototypes as needed, and for each prototype he has the same options as in Design Phase (see above), with the exception of “Create new version” and “Create Prototype” which are missing, and a new option “Move to Production”, that moves a prototype to **Production Phase**, thus concluding the product creation phase. The other actions (Edit Prototype, AR models, Feedback, Collaborations and Archive Prototype) work in a similar way as their corresponding actions in the Design Phase.

Title	Last Modified	Actions
3x3 V Pillow Cube for keychain (2nd Version)	3 days ago	[Edit] [View] [Share] [Archive]
3x3 V Pillow Cube for keychain (1st Version)	3 days ago	[Edit] [View] [Share] [Archive]

5.8. DASHBOARD - COLLABORATIONS & ARCHIVED COLLABORATIONS

Besides the list of products a user (or his organisation) is working on, two more lists of products appear in user’s dashboard (if they exist):

- Collaborations
- Archived Collaborations

In both these tabs, the user has access to designs and prototypes made by other organisations, and where the user (or his organisation) has accepted to collaborate on. The Collaborations tab contains a list of the active ones, where the Archived Collaborations contains (obviously) the archived ones. Both tabs provide access to the product and design/prototype pages of each collaboration, along with the feedback messages exchanged between the partners. For the active collaborations, the user can continue to provide feedback, while in the archived, the message thread is locked.

5.9. EXTRA PAGES

5.9.1. MESSAGES / NOTIFICATIONS / RATE COLLABORATORS

Clicking on the “envelope” icon in the navigation bar, the user has access to a messaging module, where he can see all his messages (regardless of their

type: feedback, negotiations or just personal messages with other users of the platform), notifications that he can act upon and pending rating of collaborations.

5.9.2. ABOUT PAGE

A page that contains information about the project and the platform

5.9.3. TERMS AND CONDITIONS PAGE

This page is available when someone joins ToyLabs platform, and must agree to these terms to create an account.

5.9.4. MEMBERS PAGE

Here someone can find a list of all the organisations (professional profiles) in ToyLabs platform. Visiting an organisation profile, the user can see information about that organisation: contact details, description, created in ToyLabs, competencies, certifications, awards, public content (products, designs, prototypes) etc.

6. CONCLUSIONS OF THE PILOTS ACTIVITIES

During these nine months of application of the pilots, we have seen how the initial KPIs have been mostly fulfilled: the execution times of each of the phases of creation of new toys have been reduced, costs have also been reduced in most of these phases, it has been shown that the quality of the final prototypes has increased considerably (thanks to the use of the new technologies available in the FabLabs), the process of creation of new products is executed based on the collaboration between the different actors involved in the toy sector, etc. But, we have also detected that the benefits of using the platform will increase as users perform more and more processes of creating new products using the ToyLabs Methodology and Platform. The optimal results of this project will be achieved with the continuity of the platform in the market, and with the continued use of it by the toy factories, the FabLabs, and all the actors involved. This will suppose an added motivation for the manufacturers, which will see how they increase the benefits of the use of the platform.

Anyway, during the 9 months of execution, and after the initial 3 months of preparation, the pilots have concluded with the following results:

- Creation of more than 60 products on the platform.
- A total of 223 users on the platform.
- More than 50 collaborations between different organizations.
- An assessment of 3.5 out of 5 of the platform by the different stakeholders involved.
- Reduction in the time of market analysis, partner search and design of new products.
- The complete execution of the scenarios of the two main pilots, obtaining final prototypes.
- Detection of bugs in the Platform and correction of them.
- Planning and execution of the TSIG Workshop successfully.

6.1. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS OF PARTNERS INVOLVED

6.1.1. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS OF FABLAB LECCE

For the Fablab Lecce the feedback on the use of the platform are certainly very positive.

Thanks to the Toylabs platform, fablab Lecce was able to contact not only other similar organizations on the European territory, but has also expanded its market and its sustainability by identifying a new market that was previously totally unknown. The fablab Lecce has established new relationships with toy manufacturers, has obtained opinions from experts from different sectors on its work and especially expanded its market.

The use of the platform has also changed the way we work with our customers. Feedback can only be positive, because, while working on two projects with toy makers from two countries different from ours, the use of instant messaging and of the immediate feedback that we could receive was very useful to be able to reach the final prototype as soon as possible. Very interesting was the use of the Ar that allowed us to be able to observe, to us and our customers, our prototype instantly: observe errors and propose new solutions.

Surely the toylab platform gives us the possibility to be visible to a very large number of potential customers that otherwise we could never reach. The possibility of placing on a platform regarding a specific market (toy market) our services and our skills, will certainly increase the number of jobs that we can carry out in the future. The market of fablab to date is mainly a local market and the use of the platform allows to identify new customers, impossible to identify until now. The platform will also allow to solve a problem of the fablabs.

To date, many prototypes are produced in the fablabs and many ideas are proposed, but the tools at our disposal allow us to make only prototypes. The use of the platform puts us in touch with experts, to get advice and with toy maker to make our prototypes.

In conclusion we are very pleased to have used the platform and we think it is very interesting to implement it and continue to work to be in contact with a growing number of producers, fablabs and experts from all over the world.

6.1.2. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS OF FABLAB ROMANIA

For FabLab Romania, the ToyLabs Platform is a very interesting project, full of growth potential.

We discovered a new market we were not aware we could be active in and had a chance to learn about how toymakers operate and think, although we've just scratched the surface.

The platform's design allows for both exchange of information and product visualization, which is ideal for a good conversation and it speeds up the process as we can see if changes to a design need to be made just by looking at pictures.

After being contacted by the toymaker, it was very easy to start a dialogue and we moved quickly to production. Getting feedback after every stage was also quick.

Although the sentiment and trend analysis tools are not built specifically for fablabs but rather for toymakers, we found them to be interesting, they may help us recommend a color or texture or direction in which to go with the prototype.

We are sure that, given enough time and resources to grow, ToyLabs can become a very useful tool for FabLabs, a platform where they can network, learn about manufacturing on a bigger scale and provide services to a market they have not yet addressed.

6.1.3 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS OF JUEMA

The process of creating new JUEMA dolls is very traditional. For the obtaining of prototypes, we have expert sculptors, who carry out modeling with sculptures. This is a slow process, requires a lot of patience and dedication in each of the prototypes that are produced. An added complication, which we are having in recent years, is that it is increasingly difficult to find professional sculptors, it is a profession that is being lost.

ToyLabs has allowed us to know new processes of creation of toys. With this tool we can update our way of working, and have a vision to the future to be able to transform those productive processes towards the use of more modern technologies. This reduces our dependence on professions in the process of extinction without losing the quality of the creation of prototypes that these sculptors give us. 3D printing is faster and just as accurate as the traditional process.

This, together with the other tools available on the platform, makes ToyLabs an inspiring project and whose results will help toy SMEs to be more competitive in the market.

6.1.4. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS OF V-CUBES

The experience we had during studying, designing, piloting and executing TOYLABS was overall very positive. The concept is very clever and it could be a great tool for toy manufacturers in the future. It is absolutely sure that the toy industry needs such a tool.

The platform gives the ability to the users to interact, explore and work easily. It also provides all the basic and important tools to investigate search and find the right partners for each task. It answers the most critical questions regarding the concerns and the short-term obstacles that a toy manufacturer may face while designing a new product. It reduces significantly the time and the costs involved in the development of a product and makes the life of a manager and its employees much easier.

A careful, thorough and well-designed post-exploitation and marketing program could make TOYLABS an important tool that Toy manufacturers worldwide would use frequently. Thus, it could make TOYLABS a sustainable venture.

